

ANNUARIO

DELLA SCUOLA ARCHEOLOGICA

DI ATENE E DELLE MISSIONI

ITALIANE IN ORIENTE

VOLUME 101

SCUOLA ARCHEOLOGICA ITALIANA DI ATENE

2023

ANNVARIO

DELLA

SCUOLA ARCHEOLOGICA DI ATENE

E DELLE

MISSIONI ITALIANE IN ORIENTE

VOLUME 101

SCUOLA ARCHEOLOGICA ITALIANA DI ATENE

2023

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Anvur CNR: Elenco delle riviste di classe A di Area 8 e 10, Elenco delle riviste Scientifiche di Area 8, 10 e 11; Scopus –SJR.

SCImago Journal & Country Rank: Arts and Humanities; Archeology (arts and humanities); Classics; Social Sciences;

Archeology; H Index 2; ERIHplus: Approved in 2019 according to ERIH criteria

INCLUSIONE IN DATABASE INTERNAZIONALI DI CITAZIONI E ABSTRACT

Elsevier's Scopus, abstract and citation database

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Redazione: redazione@scuoladiatene.it

Comunicazione: comunicazione@scuoladiatene.it

Sito internet: www.scuoladiatene.it

Gli articoli dell'*Annuario* sono scelti dal Comitato scientifico-editoriale e approvati da *referees* anonimi.

Scuola Archeologica Italiana di Atene

Parthenonos 14

11742 Atene

Grecia

Per le norme redazionali consultare la pagina web della Scuola alla sezione Pubblicazioni.

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Scuola Archeologica Italiana di Atene

ISSN 0067-0081 (cartaceo)

ISSN 2585-2418 (on-line)

Per l'acquisto rivolgersi a / orders may be placed to:

All'Insegna del Giglio s.a.s.

via Arrigo Boito, 50-52 - 50019 Sesto Fiorentino (FI)

www.insegnadelgiglio.it

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SKILLED LABOUR MOBILITY AND THE EARLY BYZANTINE BUILDING INDUSTRY*

YURI A. MARANO

«Λίγο ακόμα
Θα ιδούμε /
...τα μάρμαρα να λάμπουν στον ήλιο».
Γ. Σεφέρη, *Μυθιστόρημα*. ΚΓ'

Riassunto. L'articolo esamina le testimonianze letterarie, epigrafiche, documentarie e archeologiche relative alla mobilità dei tagliapietre e degli scultori nel Mediterraneo orientale durante il periodo protobizantino. Esso colloca la mobilità della manodopera specializzata nel contesto politico, sociale ed economico del periodo compreso tra il IV e gli inizi del VII sec d.C. L'articolo si sofferma in particolare su tre casi-studio relativi a Costantinopoli, all'Isauria e al Massiccio Calcereo della Siria.

Περίληψη. Το άρθρο αυτό εξετάζει τις λογοτεχνικές, επιγραφικές, γραμματειακές και αρχαιολογικές μαρτυρίες για τους πλανόδιους λιθοξόους και γλύπτες στην ανατολική Μεσόγειο κατά την πρώιμη βυζαντινή περίοδο. Εξετάζει την κινητικότητα των ειδικευμένων εργατών στο πλαίσιο των πολιτικών, κοινωνικών και οικονομικών συνθηκών που διαμόρφωσαν την οικοδομική δραστηριότητα από τον 4^ο έως τις αρχές του 7^{ου} αιώνα μ.Χ. Δίνει ιδιαίτερη έμφαση σε μελέτες περιπτώσεων από την Κωνσταντινούπολη, την Ισαυρία και τα Ασβεστολιθικά Υψίπεδα της Συρίας.

Abstract. This paper explores the literary, epigraphic, documentary, and archaeological evidence for mobile stonemasons and carvers in the eastern Mediterranean during the early Byzantine period. It contextualizes skilled labour mobility within the political, social, and economic circumstances which shaped building activity in the 4th - early 7th c. AD. It places particular emphasis on three specific case-studies from Constantinople, Isauria, and the Limestone Massif of Syria.

INTRODUCTION

Recent work over the last decades have demonstrated the importance of mobility and migration as a structural and structuring phenomenon in ancient societies¹. If the image of the ancient world as a largely immobile society is not tenable anymore, it is mainly the result of the “historiography of connectivity”, which has strongly influenced Mediterranean studies in the last twenty years². As Greg Woolf has pointed out in a recent contribution, besides the continuous references that ancient sources make to geographical mobility, there are many reasons for believing in high levels of mobility in Antiquity: the demographics of urbanisation, and the patterns of interconnectivity facilitated by the Mediterranean ecology and climate, which made mobility instrumental to survival. But, as Woolf observes, while the existence and pervasiveness of mobility in Antiquity is undisputed, human mobility is an historically empty concept if not qualified and, where possible, quantified³.

In this paper, it is our intention to address these concerns with regard to the mobility of skilled stoneworkers in the eastern Mediterranean during the early Byzantine period, from the 4th to the early 7th c. AD.

* This paper was written while I was participating as a visiting fellow in DFG-Kolleg-Forschungsgruppe 2496 “*Migration und Mobilität in Spätantike und Frühmittelalter*” at the Eberhard Karls Universität at Tübingen. I am grateful for the very fruitful conversations I had with colleagues and friends. I am also very grateful to Ben Russell, who kindly read my manuscript and discussed with me the topics

explored here.

¹ MOATTI-KAISER 2007, 9.

² The obvious reference here is to HORDEN-PURCELL 2000, 342-390.

³ WOOLF 2016.

The marble trade, the transport of stone architectural elements and furnishings, and their distribution in the early Byzantine Mediterranean are well-known and well-studied aspects⁴. However, as J. Clayton Fant observes, «long-distance trade in stone is an improbable phenomenon» in the ancient Mediterranean, where «most kinds of stone were distributed locally»⁵. Stone is dense and voluminous, and its transport, especially inland, is an expensive and risky business. While a significant amount of stone, especially white marble, did probably move around as raw material, both textual and material evidence challenge concepts of static craftsmen and “workshops”⁶. Indeed, as well attested even in other geographical areas and historical periods, also in the early Byzantine empire carvers from areas with well-known carving and quarrying traditions could move to regions where their services were in high demand and local sources of stone were available⁷. However, comparatively little attention has been devoted to skilled labour mobility in the early Byzantine building industry. Thankfully, there are exceptions, such as Eugenio Russo’s work on the mobility of Constantinopolitan carvers in the sixth-century Mediterranean⁸. More recently, Silvia Pedone has investigated the geographical range of activity of an itinerant workshop from Ephesus or Hierapolis, whose members worked on important projects in both these two cities (at the basilica of St John at Ephesus and the *martyrion* of the Apostle Philip at Hierapolis) and at Sardis in the 6th c.⁹

This paper aims to fill a gap in our knowledge of skilled labour mobility in the early Byzantine Mediterranean. The subject is vast and complex, and – though relatively abundant – the evidence provided by written, epigraphic, archaeological, and ethnoarchaeological sources poses several problems of interpretation. To trace the movements of individuals and groups demands information of a quality and quantity rarely available to ancient historians and archaeologists. As known, the interpretation of material culture as direct evidence for the mobility of peoples, groups, and individuals is fraught with difficulties. Moreover, a clear deficit in the theoretical and methodological development of archaeological research exists with regard to migration and mobility¹⁰.

Nonetheless, written and material sources at our disposal allow for the study of the mobility of skilled stoneworkers in the early Byzantine East both at a “macro-” and a “micro-level” of analysis, investigating the structural conditions (largely political, social, and economic) that shaped the phenomenon, and how these larger forces influenced the decisions and actions of individuals and groups engaged in labour migration¹¹.

A major feature of stone working, in the light of cross-cultural evidence, is the fact that we should expect more persistent patterns of mobility and itinerant lifestyle than in many other crafts¹². Mobility may have been a phenomenon of all times, but its patterns and peculiarities depended on institutional, economic, and social contexts that differed from society to society¹³. For this reason, there is a real danger in attempting to apply a single explanatory model to labour mobility. Therefore, it is necessary to adopt a case-by-case approach, asking who moved and why? How often? And how far?

To answer these questions requires a holistic approach dealing with all the available classes of evidence; these latter pose several problems and limitations, which must be addressed in detail before turning our attention to qualifying and quantifying skilled labour mobility in the early Byzantine empire.

⁴ Sculptures of Constantinopolitan manufacture are widely attested in the Aegean Sea, in Asia Minor, along the shores of the Black Sea, in the Balkans, in the Levant, in Italy, in northern Africa, in Egypt, and – beyond the frontiers of the eastern Roman empire – in Nubia and in the Aksumite kingdom (SODINI 1989; SODINI *et alii* 1998; SODINI 2002; MARANO 2016; MARSILI 2019; BALDINI 2020).

⁵ FANT 1988, 147.

⁶ RUSSELL 2013, 332-337.

⁷ This happened, for example, in the region of northern Macedonia, where during the Theodosian period the marble from the local quarries at Sivec started to be carved in a style and a quality without precedents in the region, but clearly inspired by the models of the workshops from Proconnesos and Docimium and often indistinguishable from them. Since Proconnesos and Docimium were dependent on the imperial *fiscus*, it is plausible that also the quarries at Sivec were exploited by a branch of the imperial administration. In any case this seems to have been a relatively short-term phenomenon, not outlasting the Theodosian period (NIEWÖHNER *et alii* 2013, 113-117).

⁸ RUSSO 2006; 2010.

⁹ The workshop sculpted several categories of artefacts (chancel-slabs,

column shafts, liturgical furnishings), all decorated with crosses with expanding ends and triangular “teardrops” (PEDONE 2020).

¹⁰ An overview and discussion is presented in ANTHONY 1990 and BURMEISTER 2000.

¹¹ BRETTELL-HOLLIFIELD 2023, 18-21. A similar approach has been attempted by ZERBINI 2016 for the Roman Near East.

¹² In the eastern Mediterranean craft mobility amongst stonemasons and carvers is attested since the Bronze Age (BEVAN-BLOXMAN 2016). A more recent example comes from early Medieval Italy, where the *magistri commacini* are documented in the Lombard kingdom who advertise a range of costed buildings, repair, and decorating skills (BROGIOLO 2009; on itinerant carvers in early Medieval Europe, see BEGHELLI 2020). To cite just a few other cases, in nineteenth-century France each spring some 50,000 masons from Limoges who worked on farms during the winter months reached Paris for the construction season (TILLY 1978, 53). In Greece, until the 1960s stonemasons from Langkadia in Arcadia travelled to distant places to build houses, bridges, and fountains, all in stone (ΚΩΝΣΤΑΝΤΙΝΟΠΟΥΛΟΥΣ 1970).

¹³ ROWLANDS 1971 remains a useful reminder to think critically about how craft was practised and organised in Antiquity.

MOBILITY IN THE ANCIENT WORLD: SETTING THE THEORETICAL FRAME

Mobility and migration are not exact synonyms. “Migration” is commonly used to describe mobility over long distances and permanent relocation. Migration theorists, on the other hand, use the term much more widely to encompass temporary as well as permanent movements of individuals and groups¹⁴. Nonetheless, it is unanimously recognized that, today as in the past, the majority of migratory moves consist of short-distance movements within a local area. Most of these moves take place within an information field, that represents habitually interacting social groups, and are related to changes of residence at marriage or on acquiring a better employment. In modern populations there is often a directional bias toward the major centres of employment. The prevalence of short-distance moves result primarily from the frictional effect of distance upon knowledge of variable opportunities and movement costs¹⁵.

Hence, a key variable of mobility is the economic role played by the would-be migrants and the likelihood of their skills being in demand or usable in the chosen destination. Mobility, in the same way, can be seen as a function of specialised work: migrants tend to be more skilled than many of those who stay behind. This is easily understandable, if we consider that migration is an investment in the future, and those who move need some capital to travel (also in terms of skills and labour), or else the support of backers and employers at destination. And those who most likely to migrate are those who had already done so, with the respect that mover and migrant communities provide pools of future movers and migrants¹⁶.

Mobility was over rather short distances in the ancient world. Most people stayed at or near home rather than moving over long distances, while long distance mobility was uncommon and involved a tiny proportion of the population. Those few were likely male and young, with valuable skills. The papyrological evidence from Roman Egypt testifies, for example, the circulation of traders and craftsmen within a *nomos* or between neighbouring *nomoi*, while the epigraphic evidence from Iberia and Asia Minor attests to the high proportion of merchants and skilled workers among migrants¹⁷.

The line between mobility and migration is arbitrary¹⁸, and the different categories of migration overlaps. Hence, the use of an adequate theoretical model is an essential requirement to attempt a suitable evaluation of the data. For this reason, we shall make use of the models deriving from the work of human geographers, demographers, sociologists, anthropologists, and migration historians. The recourse to these models helps to provide new analysis to mobility and migration in the ancient world. Our starting point is the scheme presented by the American sociologist and historian Charles Tilly on the definition and categorisation of migration, which has been widely cited by ancient historians¹⁹.

In a seminal article published in 1978, Tilly distinguished four main patterns of migration: a) *local migration*, defined as a movement to a “contiguous market” in labour, land, or marriage. It is expected that, in situation of local or short-distance migration, migrants engage in continuing connections with and participation in the economic and social networks within which they had lived previously; b) *circular migration*, which involves mobility over longer distances and migrants who return home in the short- or medium-term; c) *chain migration*, classified as the movement of individuals or households to a destination where people provide help, information, and encouragement to facilitate the move of new migrants; d) *career migration*, which involves individuals and households moving over considerable distances in order to pursue career opportunities created within the context of organisations, mercantile networks, governments or armies. Tilly applied this definition mainly to upper segments of society and – as the term “career” already suggest – to people who use migration for upward social and occupational mobility²⁰.

Despite its influence, Tilly’s categorisation has been recently subject to considerable criticism for being based on heterogeneous and somewhat arbitrary criteria²¹. In 2002, Lesger, Lucassen and Schrover proposed an alternative threefold typology meant to include the following criteria: a *spatial* one, corresponding to the geographical range of migration (local, regional/national, international); a *temporal* one, corresponding to the duration of the stay at the destination or destinations (temporary, circular or permanent migration); and a *modal* one, corresponding to the social and organisational aspects of mobility (personal

¹⁴ For a discussion of these distinctions see DE LIGT-TACOMA 2016.

¹⁵ ANTHONY 1990, 901-902.

¹⁶ WOOLF 2016, 452.

¹⁷ On Egypt, cf. ADAMS 2016, 271-276; on Iberia, HOLLERAN 2016, and on Asia Minor TACOMA-TYBOUT 2016.

¹⁸ TILLY 1978, 50-51.

¹⁹ *Ibid.*; TILLY 1990. For a review of the reception of Tilly’s work by ancient historians, cf. ZERBINI 2016, 306-310.

²⁰ TILLY 1978, 51-57. David Anthony distinguishes internal (short distance) migrations and external (long-distance) movements (ANTHONY 1990, 902-903).

²¹ LESGER *et alii* 2002.

network migration; organisational or non-personal migration, including career; solitary migration). The latter category is not restricted to elites or (highly) skilled movers. Artisans, journeymen, and unskilled workers, who move within a guild-like tramping system, also fit into this category²².

P. Manning offers, moreover, a simple typology of four commonly used terms to summarize most such migration: *settlers*, those who move to join an existing community that is different from their own, with the intention of remaining at their destination; *sojourners*, those moving to a new community, usually for a specific purpose, with the intention of returning to their home community; *itinerant*, those who move from community to community, but who have no single home to return to; *invaders*, those who arrive as a group in a community with the objective of seizing control rather than joining²³.

As said, written and archaeological evidence rarely allows the precise categorization of the attested cases of migration and mobility into any of Tilly's or Lesger, Lucassen and Schrover's types, which also partially overlap each other. However, as Andrea Zerbini made clear for the Roman Near East, these models can be usefully applied to the study of ancient mobility, provided that a number of caveats be observed, and further specifications added²⁴. Here we will attempt to single out some of the most relevant sources on the movement of specialised craftsmen in the early Byzantine empire from the standpoint of the functional links that bounded them to the wider social and economic structure.

In first place, it is necessary to introduce some *spatial* criteria, distinguishing between local, regional, and interregional mobility. By local, we intend all movements occurring between neighbouring villages, villages and towns or towns and towns located within a radius of a few tens of kilometres²⁵. Since many provinces had often been formed within coherent spatial-geographical frames, we may consider movement within a province as effectively movement within a region²⁶. Therefore, interregional movement can be best defined as "interprovincial"²⁷.

In *chronological* terms, the distinction between temporary, circular, and permanent migration is valid, but it is often impossible to tell them apart on the basis of the surviving evidence. Moreover, seasonal mobility due to the variable demands of both labour-intensive agriculture and pastoralism (wine and oil harvests, transhumance) or of some urban industries (building in first place) might be grouped under the heading of "temporary migration". However, some categories, such as itinerant workers moving from town to town, fit Manning's definition of "sojourners"²⁸. Finally, even though rarely attested, circular migration can be inferred on the basis of indirect evidence.

In *modal* terms, personal/group and organisational migration is exemplified by all the study-cases examined here. On the other hand, in spite of the existence of non-network or solitary migration involving individuals or households making their decision to move without having personal contacts at their destination, the common element in migration typology is the role played by personal, interpersonal and organisational networks in human mobility.

Having set the theoretical framework which will be used to analyse the mobility of stoneworkers in the early Byzantine East, we may now turn to our sources of information.

THE SOURCES: A HOLISTIC APPROACH

Working from both a re-examination of written and documentary sources and a reassessment of archaeological data, it is possible to trace labour mobility in the early Byzantine empire²⁹. However, each one of these types of evidence poses different problems that are often repeated and debated – at length – in secondary literature.

Given the well-known prejudice in ancient elite culture toward *techné* or manual, physical work involved in craft activities, it is very difficult to extrapolate information on these topics from literary sources³⁰. Artisanal

²² LESGER *et alii* 2002, 29-32.

²³ MANNING 2020, 8-9.

²⁴ ZERBINI 2016, 309-310.

²⁵ In this respect we differ from *ibid.*, 309, who by local intends all movements within a 100 km radius of the sending area. Notwithstanding this, we agree with him on the introduction of Erdkamp's urban-rural dichotomy to distinguish between the different mobility patterns between rural centres (rural-rural); from rural centres to urban centres (rural-urban), or from urban centres to villages (urban-rural);

and between urban centres (urban-urban). See ERDKAMP 2016.

²⁶ However, given that some provinces were too vast or too small, this cannot be the general rule (WOOLF 2016, 453).

²⁷ *Ibid.*, 453.

²⁸ ZERBINI 2016, 210.

²⁹ A similar approach has been adopted for the study of travelling painters in the late antique Levant by BURDAJEWICZ 2019.

³⁰ ZANINI 2006, 375-378; 2010, 269-273.

and commercial activities are therefore largely ignored by ancient authors, with a few important exceptions³¹. For example, stonemasons, carvers, and quarrymen are the workers in the building industry most frequently mentioned in hagiographic texts³². This evidence is dispersed and fragmentary, but, given its “vernacular” character, is perhaps in itself more closely related to daily life than more official written sources³³.

Among written sources, inscriptions play a crucial role, but they are rarely explicit. Nevertheless, a few Roman and early Byzantine inscriptions contain *ethnika* which allow us to determine the foreign identity of the individuals mentioned in them, as in the case of the carvers and sculptors from Proconnesos (Marmara Island, Turkey)³⁴, or in that of a certain Teoktista from Constantinople (Θεοκτίστη βυζαντία), the wife of John the stoneworker (Ἰωάννου λιθοξοῦ), who may have followed her husband to Gortyna in Crete where she was buried in the 5th/6th c.³⁵. Another source of information for the identification of itinerant groups of craftsmen are masons’ or, rather, stone-carvers’ marks, consisting of single letters carrying alphabetical or numerical meaning, as well as monograms or abbreviated names carved onto a wide range of artefacts from numerous early Byzantine contexts³⁶.

Papyri and *ostraca* shed light on the overall organisation of building sites and show how carvers and stoneworkers were employed and paid³⁷. The fact that they mainly survive from Egypt obviously raises the issue of their representativeness for the whole empire, but they are our best instrument for understanding the complex web of relationships and mechanisms that regulated the organisation of artisanal production.

In addition to the testimony of papyri and *ostraca*, we have access to legal texts (foremost amongst there are the *Codex Theodosianus* and *Codex Justinianus*) that also detail matters as the organisation and condition of craftsmen³⁸. We also possess an interesting inscription from Sardis dated to AD 459, representing a stipulation between the association of the *οικοδόμοι* and a local magistrate regarding the completion of construction works, which shed light on the legal rights, obligations, and collective identity of skilled builders³⁹.

Archaeology is less explicit in this respect. However, the evidence at our disposal creates a set of methodological conditions in which a range of interdisciplinary questions can be posed and therefore shows the vast informative potential of archaeological investigation when it equips itself with adequate tools, strategies, and objectives⁴⁰.

Our knowledge of craft activities is usually based on highly specific types of structures (kilns and furnaces, for example), remains of raw materials, specialised tools, waste, and debris from the process of production, and ultimately the finished products themselves⁴¹. In the case of itinerant carvers, unique testimony is provided by the set of stone-carving tools recovered from the first-century shipwreck off Porto Novo, Corsica, which carried a cargo mostly made up of blocks of Luna marble⁴². However, as a rule, tracing the movements of stonemasons and carvers tends to rely on the usually high problematic identification of individual objects and artefacts as the work of immigrant or itinerant artisans, on the basis of style or the skills required to work certain material⁴³. Archaeology attests, nonetheless, to different alternatives: 1) if local carvers were on hand, raw or roughed-out materials could have been ordered in from the quarries to be completed at destination; 2) if sufficient local carvers were not available, a team from elsewhere could have been hired and materials ordered in separately; or 3) marble-workers could have been contracted who would bring with them raw or roughed-out materials⁴⁴.

The upshot of this holistic approach is to overcome the patchy and fragmentary nature of archaeology and the selective and distorted picture gained through the texts. The study of documents and that of all material evidence can benefit us greatly if we integrate all the pertinent results. For this purpose, we find

³¹ Libanius and John Chrysostom devote, for example, great attention to the artisans and traders of Antioch (CERAN 2013).

³² MAGOULIAS 1976, 13-16.

³³ ZANINI 2006, 378.

³⁴ WARD-PERKINS 1980, 34.

³⁵ «Ἐνθα κατάκιτη / ἢ τῆς μακαρίας μνή/μης Θεοκτίστη Βυζαντία, σύνβιος / γενναμένη Ἰωάννου / λιθοξοῦ καὶ(αι) καλῶς τὸν / βίον διάζουσα · ἀνεπαύσατο μηνὶ Μαρτίου / · ε΄ ·, Ἰνδικτιώνος Β΄» (SEG 44.724 = KRITZAS 1994).

³⁶ PARIBENI 2004, 660-671; MARSILI 2019, 120-184.

³⁷ PAPANCONSTANTINOU forth.

³⁸ GUIDETTI 2020, 160-169; MARSILI 2019, 195-196. See, for example, the well-known imperial edict of COD.THEOD. 13.4.2 of AD 337 releasing several categories of artisans from compulsory public services.

Included in the list are architects, stonecutters, stonemasons, painters, sculptors, statue makers, mosaicists, and marble-workers.

³⁹ GARNSEY 1998; DI BRANCO 2000. The most exact parallel for our text can be found at Rome (*AEpigr* 1941, 68), where an inscription found at Sant’Omobono in 1937 provides a crucial piece of evidence on the reorganisation of the *collegium fabrum tignariorum* between AD 296 and 312 (FABIANO 2019).

⁴⁰ ZANINI 2006, 405.

⁴¹ HELMEYER 2004; ZANINI 2006, 396. A good study-case is the Pottery Quarter of Sagalassos (MURPHY-POBLOME 2011).

⁴² BERNARD *et alii* 1998, 59-64.

⁴³ RUSSELL 2013, 335-336.

⁴⁴ SODINI 1989, 169-170; 2002, 134-135.

it necessary to begin with an overview of the terminology used to describe stoneworkers and carvers in the written sources before we can turn our attention to three specific study-cases of mobility of travelling craftsmen in the early Byzantine eastern Mediterranean.

CONSTRUCTION WORKERS AND STONECARVERS IN WRITTEN AND LITERARY SOURCES

Construction workers included a variety of specialised and technical professionals and skilled and unskilled labour force, from “architects” and “engineers” to day labourers. Unfortunately, Byzantine terminology used to identify workers by skill is generic or vague, and workers are often lumped together with a distinction made only between skilled and unskilled labourers⁴⁵. If the term *ἐργάται* was used for unskilled workers, the category of more specialised stoneworkers comprised a great variety of skills, which are iconographically attested. Depictions of building workers were not uncommon in late Roman art, as the vignette of the *Vergilius Romanus* consisting of the Building of Carthage demonstrates⁴⁶. But the sequence of thirty-two panels on the E vault of the large basilical hall in the Umayyad palace at Qusayr ‘Amra near Amman (Jordan) is exceptionally rich: we may note stonemasons squaring blocks, loading them onto camels, and building walls, carpenters and smiths, and labourers preparing mortars, all at work during what seem to be the initial stages of the construction of the palace itself (Fig. 1)⁴⁷.

Nonetheless, the lack of precision in terminology precludes identification of the specific nature of single types of works, and specialisms were not mutually exclusive, given that specialists had to be able to adapt their output when demand for their skills was unpredictable or seasonal⁴⁸.

A partial exception concerns the term *μηχανικός* or *μηχανοποιός* indicating comprehensively trained “architects/engineers” equally versed in the theoretical (geometry, arithmetic, astronomy, and physics) and practical (metallurgy, construction, carpentering, and pictorial art) aspects of architecture and engineering⁴⁹. *Mechanikoi* were active at Constantinople (as the architects of Hagia Sophia, Anthemius of Tralles and Isidore of Miletus) and in the provinces (Dara in Mesopotamia, Zenobia-Halebiyye and Resafa-Sergiopolis in Syria, in the Balkans), where they oversaw the planning and execution of major imperially sponsored projects⁵⁰.

In contrast to *mechanikoi* and *mechanopoiioi*, the term *ἀρχιτέκτων* signified an experienced master builder and contractor with technical expertise, practical knowledge, and supervisory abilities. The *ἀρχιτέκτων* was an administrator and supervisor responsible for procuring building material and equipment, hiring and managing the workforce and, in general, directing the building works⁵¹. Moreover, the terms *οικοδόμος* and *τεχνίτης* can be viewed as synonym for *architekton*, with whom shared a similar, eminently practical knowledge⁵². The distinction among *architektones*, *oikodomoι* and *technitai* is unclear, and it may be possible that the terminology related to their professions lost its specificity as did their individual responsibilities. In their capacity of master builders, they were in charge of the planning and construction of building projects and oversaw hired workmen. The latter were grouped under the already-mentioned umbrella term *ἐργάται*, as suggested by a mosaic inscription from a church of St Theodoros in the area of Bostra (?) mentioning the villagers who provided both the salaries of the *τεχνίται* and the workforce (*ἐργάτας*)⁵³.

⁴⁵ For the early Byzantine period, see MENTZOY 1975, 169-194; SODINI 1979, 75-80; ΚΡΙΤΙΚΑΚΟΥ 1990; BORGIA 2012; MARSILI 2019, 207-220. For the middle Byzantine period, cf. OUSTERHOUT 1999, 43-57 and BOURAS 2002.

⁴⁶ Other examples are provided by the miniature depicting the building of Solomon’s Temple in the probably fourth-century *Quedlinburger Itala*, by the miniature in the sixth-century *Ilias Ambrosiana* which shows the Greek soldiers at Troy setting up camp and feasting (PRAYON 1986), and by a sixth-century mosaic from Oued Rmel in the Zaghuan region (Tunisia) consisting of a scene of the construction of a building (DUNBABIN 1978, 192). The synagogue at Khirbet Wadi Hamam is decorated with a mosaic floor dated to the late 3rd - early 4th c. depicting the construction of the Tower of Babel (?) and a total of 13 craftsmen, including carpenters, builders mixing mortar, and a stonemason (LEIBNER-MILLER 2010, 241-249).

⁴⁷ ALMAGRO *et alii* 1975, 65-66; VIBERT-GUIGUE 2004; TARAGAN 2008.

⁴⁸ For example, in eighteenth-century England, stonemasons were also

sculptors, since otherwise they would be unemployed for at least four months of the year, when building sites were inaccessible (RUSSELL 2020, 251).

⁴⁹ On the formation and prerogatives of *μηχανικοί* and *μηχανοποιός*, cf. DOWNEY 1948/49; SCHIBILLE 2009; ZANINI 2007, 390-394.

⁵⁰ *Ibid.*, 389-392. The activities of the imperial *μηχανικός* Viktorinos are well documented in monumental epigraphy from Epirus Vetus, Moesia, Scythia, Thrace, and Illyricum, where he was in charge of the building of fortifications under Justinian (FEISSEL 1988; 2000, 92-93).

⁵¹ The *τεχνίται* also included figure-painters, wall-painters, mosaicists, masons, and carpenters. Yet, in *De aedificiis* Procopius uses the term for “military engineers” (MILSON 2003, 161).

⁵² In Syria, *architektones* are attested more regularly in the central part of the country, while the attested *technitai* seem to have dwelt mainly in the Belus region (ZANINI 2007, 395).

⁵³ «+ Κύριε ὁ Θεὸς τοῦ ἁγίου Θεοδώρου βοήθῃ πᾶσιν τοῖς / κατοικοῦσιν τὴν κώμην δι’ οὗ ἐπόρ-/ <γ>ησαν τὰ ἀναλόματα τῶν τεχνιτῶ(ν) (καὶ) τοὺς ἐργάτας» (SEG 45.2028 = GATIER-VILLENEUVE 1993, 4-5).

Fig. 1. Qusayr 'Amra, main hall, E wall: scenes from the building of the palace (after VIBERT-GUIGUE 2004; © Claude Vibert-Gague).

The terms (attested since the Archaic/Classical period) most used for the craftsmen who worked in stone (λιθοξόοι, λαοξόοι, λαξόοι, λααξόοι, λατόμοι and λιθουργοί) embrace the entire range of activities in the process of preparation of raw materials, from their extraction and roughing out to carving⁵⁴. An invocation carved on the face of an ancient quarry found at Kirtaş (Uşak, Turkey), on the borders between Phrygia and Lydia, draws a distinction between λιθοξόοι (stone-squarers) and λατόμοι (quarrymen)⁵⁵, but these terms were overarching titles which covered numerous specialisms involved in the production and carving of stone and reflect the versatility required from craftsmanship in these trades⁵⁶. Not by chance, several *lithoxoi* are known through signatures on architectural elements from different sites in Asia Minor and Syria⁵⁷. In the letter written after 373 to his first cousin, bishop Amphilochius of Iconium, about the construction of an octagonal *martyrion*, Gregory of Nyssa also details his plan for the completion of the entire structure that included the expertise of skilled stoneworkers (λιθοξόοι) for the finishing, facing, and carving of the roughed-out architectural elements (pillars, bases, capitals, and lintels) of the building (*infra*).

More precise terminology clearly refers to stoneworkers specialised in marble: λευκουργός indicates a worker in white marble, while μαρμαράριος and its variants (μαρμάρ(ε)ιος, μαρμαράς, μαρμάρης, μαρμαράρις) clearly means “marble worker”. This may imply a narrowing down of the semantic spectrum of μαρμαράριος, a Greek word of Latin origin (after *marmorarius*), which in the Roman period indicated not only carvers and sculptors, but also described contractors specialising in supplying and working marble⁵⁸. An inscription carved on a fourth-to-fifth century pilaster-capital from a bath-complex at Tiberias (*Palaestina Secunda*) mentions the μαρμαράριος Abraham who carved it⁵⁹ (Fig. 2). In a similar fifth/sixth century inscription reused in the Ibrahimi Mosque at Hebron the marble-worker Nilos invokes the help of God for him and his family⁶⁰.

⁵⁴ BORGIA 2012, 56-60; MARSILI 2019, 214-217. In his *Homily in the Praise of Theodore the Recruit* Gregory of Nyssa remembers a λιθοξόος «who polished the stones until they had the smoothness of silver» (MANGO 1972, 36).

⁵⁵ «Ὁ θεὸς τῆς δόξης σου β/σθήτης/σιν τοῖς / λιθοξοῖς καὶ λατόμοις / τῆς λαμπρᾶς καὶ φιλοσεβᾶς[...?] / καὶ φιλο...» (SEG 30.1397 = PRALONG 1980, 259-262).

⁵⁶ Similarly, in Latin the same terms could be similarly associated with different specialisms (RUSSELL 2013, 205-208).

⁵⁷ At Hierapolis, a λιθοξοός (*sic*) Trophimus signed one of the blocks in the apse of the local cathedral; at Güllbahçe (ancient Tautala, nearby Izmir), a λιθοξοός (*sic*) Timotheus signed a cornice of the local church; in Syria Apamene, at Taroūtīn (Tarountia Emporon) and at Ḥalbān two architraves bear the names of the λιθοξόος John (AD 510-511) and of the λιθοξόοι John and Symeon (AD 543) respectively; from Ḥalbān

is also a pier-colonnette signed by Leontios λιθοξόος (for this and other evidence, see MARSILI 2019, 214-215).

⁵⁸ A Hellenized form of the Latin *marmorarius*, the term makes its appearance in the 3rd c., but it occurs mainly in the late antique and early Byzantine period: FISCHER 1998, 40-43; EAA IV, s.v. «*marmorarius*», 870-875 [I. Calabi Limentani].

⁵⁹ «Ἡ Θεοῦ χάρις / μετὰ / Ἀβραμίου / μαρμάρ(αρ)ίου» (FISCHER 1998, 269-272).

⁶⁰ «[+] Ἄγιε Ἀβράμα, βώηθι τὸν <δ>οῦ/λόν σου Νίλον τὸν δ<ἐ> μαρμα/ράριον / καὶ Ἀγαθήμερον / καὶ Ὑγιαν καὶ Ὡμαβίς καὶ Θω/μασίαν καὶ Ἀβδάλλα καὶ Ἀνα/στασίαν» (SEG 8.240 = FISCHER 1998, 272-273). Finally, a couple of papyri mentions a category of stonecutters (στυλοποιός), expert in the manufacture of column-shafts: PAPA-CONSTANTINOU forth.

Fig. 2. Tiberias, bath-complex: inscription on a pilaster-capital mentioning the μαρμαράριος Abraham (after FISCHER 1998).

«...ARTISANS FROM THE WHOLE WORLD»: CONSTANTINOPOLITAN STONEMEN ABROAD

Describing in considerable detail the building of Hagia Sophia in Constantinople, the anonymous author of the ninth-century *Narration on Hagia Sophia* (*Enarratio de aedificatione templi S. Sophiae*) states that the workforce consisted of

a hundred master craftsmen (τεχνίται μαίστορες), and each of whom had a hundred men, so that all together there were ten thousand. Fifty master craftsmen with their people were building the right-hand side, and the other fifty were likewise building the left-hand side, so that the work would proceed quickly, in competition and haste⁶¹.

It is generally accepted that the *Narration* pertains to a period and conceptual world in which reality has been largely supplanted by myth and its wealth of factual detail is often deceptive and widely preposterous⁶². However, the *Narration* is, of all the texts bearing on Justinian's Great Church, one of the most captivating, and we can agree with Cyril Mango when he claims that «it is almost a pity to subject such charming legend to historical criticism»⁶³. While its descriptions are made up of legendary elements and standard ekphrastic features, the *Narration* offers a fascinating entry into the reality of the process of the construction of Hagia Sophia. The Great Church marked the heyday of church-building in the Byzantine Empire, and no equivalent structure was constructed in the subsequent millennium. Thus, the engagement of a huge workforce in its construction is consistent with the scale and complexity of the project.

The enormous building enterprise at Hagia Sophia epitomises the extraordinary levels of artistic production of the age of Justinian, with the emperor himself an energetic patron of the arts. As Procopius states, the emperor «disregarding all questions of expense, eagerly pressed on to begin the work of construction, and began to gather all the artisans from the whole world»⁶⁴.

The imperial court and clerical elites followed his lead throughout the empire, and their building activity contributed a great deal to the spread of a broadly Constantinopolitan style and helped to

⁶¹ ANON. *enarr. S. Sophiae* 1.7: «Υπήρχον δὲ τεχνίται μαίστορες ἑκατὸν, ἔχοντες ἕκαστος αὐτῶν ἀνὰ ἑκατὸν ἀνδρῶν, ὁμοῦ γινόμενοι χιλιάδες δέκα. Καὶ οἱ μὲν πενήκοντα μαίστορες μετὰ τοῦ λαοῦ αὐτῶν τὸ δεξιὸν μέρος ὠκοδομοῦν, οἱ δὲ ἕτεροι πενήκοντα ὁμοίως τὸ ἐξώτερον μέρος ὠκοδομοῦν διὰ τὸ εἰς ἔριν καὶ σπουδὴν ταχέως κτίσασθαι τὸ ἔργον» (transl. MANGO 1972, 97).

⁶² *Id.* 1992. On the composition and transmission of the *Diegesis*, see

DAGRON 1984, 191-314; BRUBAKER 2001, 80-87; OUSTERHOUT 2002.

⁶³ MANGO 1992, 45.

⁶⁴ PROCOP. *Aed.* 1.1.23: «ὁ μὲν οὖν βασιλεὺς ἀφροντιστήσας χρημάτων ἀπάντων ἐς τὴν οἰκοδομὴν σπουδῆ ἴετο, καὶ τοὺς τεχνίτας ἐκ πάσης γῆς ἡγερεῖν ἅπαντας».

shape artistic and architectural production in Constantinople and in the provinces as well. Official building projects, which implied the transfer of human capital in the form of skilled specialists and the export of high-quality materials, served as imperial propaganda and offer opportunity to investigate the interaction between the Centre of the empire and its internal Peripheries⁶⁵. This intense exchange of information between Constantinople and local communities created condition for the distribution of knowledge and represented a unifying ideological element, since both areas shared significant and symbolic forms of material culture⁶⁶.

Imperial and high-status patrons could supply both raw materials or roughed-out elements and the workers needed to carve them⁶⁷. As seen, artisans who travel for specific commissions can be generally grouped under the heading “organisation migration”, which – according to Lesger, Lucassen and Schrover’s categorisation – involves individuals and groups moving in response to employment and career opportunity created within the context of large organisation, such as mercantile networks, governments, or armies⁶⁸.

A good example of this kind of organisation is the Lechaion basilica at the western harbour of Corinth⁶⁹. Dated between the last decades of the 5th and the mid-6th c.⁷⁰, this monumental complex, thought to have been dedicated to the martyr Leonidas⁷¹, comprised the proper basilica (a three-aisled church with a tripartite transept and a half-domed apse), a forecourt, a semi-circular atrium, and a baptistery. The size of the church (180 meters long, comparable with the Constantinian basilica of Saint Peter in Rome) and the lavish use of Proconnesian marble for its architectural decoration, floor and wall revetments are all suggestive of an imperially sponsored project⁷².

Different groups of carvers working alongside side each other on the construction site of the Lechaion basilica can be identified on stylistic grounds. A set of architectural elements comprises column bases and shafts drums, Ionic impost capitals, architraves, and cornices, all carved in Proconnesian marble and sculpted in an unmistakably Constantinopolitan style. Moreover, the discovery of a roughed out composite capital and a column-base (Fig. 3), both in Proconnesian marble, are suggestive of the presence of itinerant teams of carvers who arrived at Corinth from Constantinople to work on the architectural decoration of the Lechaion basilica⁷³. This is further confirmed by the discovery of several items bearing the mason’s

⁶⁵ MUNDELL MANGO 2003. On the relation between Constantinople and the provinces of the Early byzantine Empire as seen through the lens of official building projects, see also ZANINI 2021.

⁶⁶ ZANINI 2007, 386-387; BOERO 2022, 237.

⁶⁷ On the role of secular and ecclesiastic patrons, see ZANINI 2010, 266-269; SODINI 2013; MARANO 2016, 127-132; MARSILI 2016.

⁶⁸ LESGER *et alii* 2002, 30-32.

⁶⁹ PALLAS 1977, 165-171 (with previous bibliography).

⁷⁰ On the basis of numismatic evidence, Pallas posited the reign of Marcian (AD 450-457) as a *terminus ante quem* for the construction of the basilica, and the reign of Justin I (AD 518-527) for its completion. Pallas also suggested that the building was destroyed by the earthquakes of AD 551/552 (ΠΑΛΛΑΣ 1966, 159 and 166-167). This reconstruction has been challenged by K.W. Slane and G. Sanders, according to whom the complex shows no sign of earthquake damage, while the reconsideration of the ceramic evidence from the site points to a mid-6th c. chronology (SLANE-SANDERS 2005, 291-294). A later chronology is also compatible with the characteristics of the masons’ marks carved on the architectural elements of the basilica (MARSILI 2019, 157-161). Things, however, are further complicated by a recent study by C. Tsigonaki, who ascribes the sculptural decoration from the excavation to the second half of the 5th c. and reports the presence of sign of earthquake induced soil liquefaction in the nave and aisles of the basilica (TSIGONAKI 2020).

⁷¹ LIMBERIS 2006, 450-452. Leonidas of Corinth has been often confused with a namesake fifth-century bishop of Athens. This identification has led to the erroneous identification of the Ilisos basilica at Athens with the “basilica of Leonidas”. This confusion is based on a passage of Michael Choniates, who in the 13th c. mixed to traditions into one and stated that Leonidas was a bishop of Athens: BREYTENBACH-TZAVELLA 2023, 424-425.

⁷² The basilica was a prominent landmark for those looking N from the city toward the Gulf of Corinth and for travellers arriving by land and sea. Its construction can be considered part of a larger imperial project aimed at enhancing the monumental and religious prestige of

Lechaion, one of the main ports of the early Byzantine empire and a major stop-over along the E-W Mediterranean routes. Archaeological evidence and written sources also attest to the attention paid by imperial authorities to large scale harbour facilities at the Lechaion between the 4th and the 6th c. (BROWN 2018, 66-68).

⁷³ SODINI 1977, 424-426; TSIGONAKI 2020, 244-249. The intervention of Constantinopolitan carvers highlights the prestige of this and other projects here analysed. The survey conducted by Nuşin Asgari in the quarries of Proconnesos have brought to light 541 architectural elements in all the phases of their production. It has been shown that, in addition to the export of simple blocks, there was on the one hand mass-production of standard items (Corinthian and Ionic capitals in first place), and on the other the execution of special, more elaborate artefacts (ASGARI 1993). The first class of extensively prefabricated artefacts was usually exported ready for use, with only assembly and some finishing required on the building site. The clearest example of this practice comes from the Marzamemi shipwreck, sunken off the southeastern tip of Sicily in the first quarter of the 6th c. (KAPITÄN 1961; 1980; for the dating, see LEIDWANGER *et alii* 2021, 310). The cargo, originated at Constantinople, but whose destination remains unknown, comprised some (but not all) the decorative elements for one church, with an additional and uncertain number of elements for a second (religious or secular) structure: at least 32 column shafts, 35 (or more) Corinthian capitals of the so-called Kautzsch VII type, various pier-colonnettes and slabs pertaining to a chancel screen and an altar table, all in Proconnesian marble, and an ambo in *verde antico* from Thessaly, for a total weight of around 95 tons of stone (*ibid.*, 300-302). This suggests that the commissioner or the commissioners of these elements many have had access to skilled carvers but did not need to have access to them in large numbers or necessarily upon the arrival of the imported elements (RUSSELL-LEIDWANGER 2020, 238). On the contrary, more elaborate items, like the basket capitals with fine and fragile lattice decoration, required to be finished on place, as demonstrated by the large quantities of waste cores from drill-works which served as packing for the floor of the nave of the church of St Polyeuctos in Constantinople (HARRISON 1986, 163; 1989, 80).

Fig. 3. Corinth, Lechaion basilica: roughed out column-base in Proconnesian marble (photo A.; © ΥΠΡΟΑ, ΓΔΑΠΚ, Ephorate of Antiquities of Corinth).

mark ΖΩ or ΩΖ, to be read as Ζώ[στυμος], also attested on architectural elements from Constantinople, Thessaloniki, Athens, Varna, Ravenna and Poreč⁷⁴.

Alongside these materials, excavations have recovered a second set of elements (Ionian capitals, impost and corbel capitals, cornices), sculpted in a fine-grained white marble, which display the style and formal repertoire of fifth-sixth century sculpture from the Peloponnese, Attica, and Boeotia. Decorated with the standard motifs of reed, lancet or lotus leaves often framing cross medallions, these items were possibly carved by local craftsmen, who worked side by side with Constantinopolitan sculptors⁷⁵.

The dispatch of teams of workers with their materials to a building site might well have been a relatively cheap option for large projects, which would in any case already exorbitantly expensive. In other cases, teams of carvers could be dispatched to work local materials at destination.

Direct copies of Constantinopolitan artefacts are known from the Basilica B at Philippi in Macedonia, built around AD 540 on the site of the Macellum and the Palaestra, to the S of the city forum. This impressive three-aisled basilica with a transept was preceded by an atrium and an exonarthex and possessed a brick-built ribbed dome, that rose directly above the sanctuary⁷⁶. This dome shares the features of the second dome of Hagia Sophia, which replaced the first one collapsed in AD 558. This is not the place to discuss the chronological discrepancies between the two buildings and the experimental character the dome of Basilica B, that would have anticipated the solution adopted in the Great Church⁷⁷. It is, however, clear that its architects must have belonged to the circle of builders active in Constantinople at the time.

The same holds true for the carvers responsible for the architectural sculpture of the building: the basket capitals, the impost capitals with paired branches, and the imposts decorated with cornucopias from Basilica B have direct parallels in Hagia Sophia and in the Basilica A at Beyazıt at Constantinople, although

⁷⁴ MARSILI 2019, 158-161, 358-366.

⁷⁵ SODINI 1977, 426; TSGONAKI 2020, 244-245.

⁷⁶ The church may have not been fully completed at the time when it was heavily damaged in the earthquake of AD 540 (LEMERLE 1945, 413-513, remains the crucial study of Basilica B).

⁷⁷ If the vaulting of Basilica B was completed by AD 540, it would suggest the possibility that Isidore the Younger, who rebuilt the dome of Hagia Sophia after AD 558, may have worked in Philippi

first. It is otherwise possible that the dome of Basilica B replaced an earlier structure damaged or collapsed in the catastrophic event of 540 AD, requiring an alternative solution that may have resulted in the dome we know (ĆURČIĆ 2010, 207-209; on the close ties between the Basilica B and Constantinople, see also ΒΕΛΕΝΗΣ 2002). The presence of a double ramp ambo, located along the main axis of the church, points further to Constantinople (JAKOBS 1987, 227-229).

Fig. 4. a) Philippi, basilica B: basket capital (photo A.; © ΥΠΠΟΑ, ΓΔΑΠΚ, Ephorate of Antiquities of Kavala); b) Istanbul, Hagia Sophia, northern gallery: basket capital with monogram medallion (after ANTONIAΔΟΥ 1907).

they were carved in the grey marble from the quarries of Central Macedonia and not in that from the Proconnesian ones (Fig. 4a-b)⁷⁸.

In Asia Minor, Justinian's Basilica of St John at Ephesus similarly stands out in its local context thanks to its cruciform plan of six modular bays, domes, and sculpture⁷⁹. Much of the marble decoration was made by Constantinopolitan carvers: the bases and column-shafts were imported finished from the quarries of Proconnesos⁸⁰, while the Ionian impost capitals and pilaster capitals, which show a mixture of Constantinopolitan and regional styles, were imported in a quarry state and presumably carved on the spot by Constantinopolitan sculptors with the assistance of local craftsmen⁸¹.

At Seleucia in Isauria (today Ayatekla Meriamlik, in Turkey), Evagrius Scholasticus attributes to the emperor Zeno (AD 474-491) the dedication of «a huge sanctuary (μέγιστον τέμενος) of outstanding magnificence and beauty to the protomartyr Thecla»⁸². The shrine comprised at least three churches, a bathhouse, and several large cisterns. While there is no consensus among scholars as to which buildings can be attributed to Zeno⁸³, the great quantities of Proconnesian marble elements (Corinthian, Ionian impost, double-zone, and basket capitals) lavished on the sanctuary are a clear indicator of imperial support. However, architectural decoration also includes several artefacts carved in local stone copying Constantinopolitan models⁸⁴.

⁷⁸ LEMERLE 1945, 500-510; SODINI 1984, 245. The excavations at the Basilica B also recovered several fragments of chancel slabs carved in the calcitic marble from Cape Phanari on Thasos: HERRMANN *et alii* 1998, 333. Another group of unfinished sixth-century capitals have been near the Roman Agora of Philippi, nearby the Basilica B (PANAYOTIDI 1972).

⁷⁹ The exact date of Justinianic remodelling remains uncertain. The new basilica was probably initiated in AD 535/536 by bishop Hypatios, one of the chief ecclesiastical advisers to Justinian. The lack of homogeneity in the church fabric, however, indicates at least two building phases: in contrast to the chancel and transept, the longer west arm and perhaps upper portions were completed under imperial patronage within the sixth decade of the 6th c.: HÖRMANN 1951, 51, 69, 100 and 297; DEICHMANN 1974, 562-567; FOSS 1979a, 87-91 and 129-151; BÜYÜKKOLANCI 1995; THIEL 2005, 1-111; KARYDIS 2011, 8-13 and 69-107; RUSSO 2016, 292.

⁸⁰ VETTERS 1973, 83-184; DEICHMANN 1974, 564-565; RUSSO 2016, 271. Cf. MARSILI 2019, 256-258, for masons' marks indicating elements that came from Proconnesian quarries and were most likely imperial contributions.

⁸¹ DEICHMANN 1974, 562-564 and 566-567; RUSSO 1999, 30-34,

39-47, 50-51; 2016, 269-272.

⁸² EVAGR. *h.e.* 3.8: «Οὗτος ὁ Ζήνων μέγιστον τέμενος, ἐξοχῆ τε καὶ κάλλει προύχον ἀνατέθεικε τῇ πρωτομάρτυρι Θεέκλῃ ἀνὰ τὴν Σελευκείων τὴν πρὸς τῇ Ἰσαύρων χώρα κειμένην, πλείστοις καὶ βασιλικαῖς ἀναθήμασι διακοσμήσας, τοῖς καὶ μέχρις ἡμῶν σωζομένοις» (transl. WHITBY 2000, 142). According to Evagrius, Zeno erected the «μέγιστον τέμενος» as an expression of his gratitude to saint Thecla who appeared before him, who was then exiled in Isauria by the usurper Basiliscus, predicting his return to power (KOSIŃSKI 2010, 79-97).

⁸³ S. Hill suggests that Zeno supported the construction of both the main churches at Meriamlik (the three-aisled basilica and the so-called Cupola Church) as well as some of the ancillary buildings of the complex such as the bathhouse and cisterns (HILL 1996, 213-214). However, according to H. Elton, the third basilica, the North Church, may have been paid for by local patrons: ELTON 2002, 153.

⁸⁴ SODINI 1987, 231-242. The use of Proconnesian marble also characterizes two other Zeno's building projects, as the shrine of St Menas in the Nile Delta (SEVERIN-SEVERIN 1987) and that of the Mother of God on Mount Garizim in Samaria (SCHNEIDER 1951, 221-230).

Fig. 5. Rome, Ponte Salario: the parapets and pier-colonnettes as depicted in one engraving by J.B.L.G. Seroux D'Agincourt, *Histoire de l'art par les monuments, depuis sa décadence au IV^e siècle jusqu'à son renouvellement*, Paris 1823 (after GUIGLIA GUIDOBALDI 2002).

Another important, but often neglected example comes from the Ponte Salario in Rome, destroyed by the Ostrogothic king Totila and later reconstructed by Narses in AD 565. The bridge is now an almost entirely modern structure, but old drawings and prints show a series of parapets with interlacing rhomboids bearing, at their centre, equal armed crosses with expanded ends and six-petalled flowers, fixed between pier-colonnettes crowned by conical ends and circular ones, the latter decorated with crosses and flowers (Fig. 5)⁸⁵. These decorative motifs find parallels in Constantinople, Syria, and Egypt, and provide compelling evidence as to the presence in Rome of carvers from the imperial capital and/or the eastern Mediterranean accompanying the army, as attested in the written sources⁸⁶.

«...THE WORKERS IN YOUR REGION ARE BETTER FOR OUR NEED THAN THOSE THAT CAN BE HIRED HERE»: ISAURIAN STONEMEN

In this year [AD 558] on Tuesday, 7 May, in the 5th hour, while the dome of the Great Church was being repaired (for it had been cracked during the preceding earthquakes) and while the Isaurians were working on it (ἐργαζομένων τῶν Ἰσαύρων), the eastern part of the vault of the holy sanctuary collapsed and crushed the ciborium, the holy table, and the altar⁸⁷.

This well-known passage of the *Chronicle* of Theophanes Confessor, ultimately deriving from Malalas, and common to many other Byzantine chroniclers, is one of the best-known sources concerning the

⁸⁵ GUIGLIA GUIDOBALDI 2002, 1491-1497; Russo 2006, 260-268. The presence at Rome of carvers from Constantinople or trained there can also be deduced on the basis of two double-zone capitals from the basilica of San Clemente created in Luna marble in an unmistakably Constantinopolitan style (GUIDOBALDI 1992; Russo 2006, 247-261).

⁸⁶ That the early Byzantine army had a corps of skilled craftsmen is suggested by Procopius, who relates three episodes in which Belisarius' Isaurian troops in Italy acted as engineers, during the siege of Naples in AD 536 when they broke through a blockage in an aqueduct, at

Rimini in AD 538 when they dug a trench, and at Osimo in AD 539 when they demolished a cistern (ELTON 2000, 299).

⁸⁷ THEOPHANES *Chron.* AM 6051 [AD 558/559]: «Τούτω τῷ ἔτει μηνι Μαΐω ζ', ἡμέρα γ', ὥρα ε', φιλοκαλουμένου τοῦ τρούλλου τῆς μεγάλης ἐκκλησίας, (ἦν γὰρ διεργημένος ἐκ τῶν γενομένων σεισμῶν) ἐργαζομένων τῶν Ἰσαύρων, ἔπεσε τὸ ἀνατολικὸν μέρος τῆς προὔπιστολης τοῦ ἁγίου θυσιαστηρίου καὶ συνέτριψε τὸ κιβώριον καὶ τὴν ἁγίαν τράπεζαν καὶ τὸν ἄμβωνα» (transl. MANGO *et alii* 1997, 341).

activity of Isaurian stonemasons in the early Byzantine empire. The presence of Isaurian craftsmen in Constantinople was not an isolated phenomenon since several texts attest to the flow of Isaurian artisans to various provinces of the Empire as early as the late 4th c.⁸⁸

In Antiquity, the area of Isauria was known under the general name of Cilicia, corresponding roughly to the sub-division of *Cilicia Tracheia* (Rough Cilicia). Unlike the rich and populous plains of *Cilicia Pedias* to the W, *Cilicia Tracheia* was a rugged limestone territory extending in south-eastern Anatolia between the fertile Adana plain drained by the Seyhan Görksu and the Seyhan, and the mountain ranges of the Taurus to the W and the N, and the Hatay to the E.⁸⁹

A notorious hotbed for banditry, Isauria exported human capital in the form of skilled labour as well. Scholars argued that the flux of Isaurian stoneworkers to the various provinces of the early Byzantine empire was due to the turmoil and civil wars that ravaged the region at the end of the 5th c.⁹⁰ However, the diaspora of Isaurian master builders and stoneworkers does not indicate economic and political difficulties at home. On the contrary, Isaurians are documented outside their homeland well before this period, and between the 5th and 6th c. Isauria experienced a long phase of prosperity reflected in large-scale architectural activity in towns and villages across the area.⁹¹ The rich epigraphic evidence testifies nonetheless to the strength of building trades in the economy of late antique Cilicia.⁹² Thus, the case of Isauria clearly illustrates the close connection between the availability of stone (limestone mostly), its quarrying, and the acquisition of skills necessary to work it.⁹³ Moreover, the activity of Isaurian stoneworkers confirms the “multi-vocal” character of Byzantine architecture of the 5th to the 7th c., when – as Enrico Zanini observes – a variety of coexisting and propulsive centres played a relevant role in the artistic production of the time.⁹⁴

Gregory of Nyssa’s *Letter 25* to his cousin Amphilochius, bishop of Iconium (present-day Konya), offers evidence for the mobility of stoneworkers from southern Anatolia and gives remarkable insight in the construction of a *martyrion* and into relations between management and skilled labour.⁹⁵ The letter, a follow-up to previous correspondence, contains a lengthy description of the building and its interior decoration, which at first sight appears to be a proper *ekphrasis*. Yet this is not the case. As the designer and contractor of the project (we do not know if he hired an architect), Gregory draws a *memorandum*, cataloguing the materials and technical expertise he needs to achieve his architectural and devotional goals.⁹⁶ The letter reveals how far Gregory would extend himself financially and personally to provide his flock with a suitable place to tribute homage to the martyrs.⁹⁷

It is not easy to grasp the exact meaning of his words and to render them in contemporary architectural language, but Gregory describes a *martyrion* consisting of a central octagonal space crowned with a roof shaped like a “pinecone” (most probably a spherical dome), and four radiating arms so as to give a cruciform plan.⁹⁸ In addition, a forty columns peristyle surrounded the complex on all sides, a detail that suggests dedication to the Forty Martyrs of Sebasteia, with whom Gregory and his family long had connections.⁹⁹

No trace of Gregory’s *martyrion* survives, but several extant buildings give insight into what it looked like.¹⁰⁰ However, the *martyrion* of St. Philip at Hierapolis in Phrygia offers a nearly contemporary, though

⁸⁸ For Isaurian builders and stoneworkers working at different building sites, see MANGO 1966; for Isaurians in hagiographical sources, cf. MAGOULIAS 1976, 13-16.

⁸⁹ For a detailed discussion of the geography and name of Isauria, see MILTON 1980, 1230-1234.

⁹⁰ In Isauria, the assumption of power by Zeno, who was of Isaurian origin himself, was followed by a succession of rebellions and usurpations – those of Basiliscus (AD 475-476) and of Illus and Leontius (AD 484-488). Even Anastasius upon his accession had to face a revolt in the region: rebels were curbed in late AD 492, though it took six years to reduce their various strongholds (MANGO 1966, 363-364; see also HILL 1996, 8, and ELTON 2000, 299-300).

⁹¹ VARINLIOĞLU 2007.

⁹² Some 456 funerary inscriptions have survived from Korykos, in which individuals identified either themselves or those whom they commemorated by citing titles. The building trades are a small part of this sample, but a significant one: four *marmorarii*, two *latomoi*, three *oikodomoi*, four *tektones* one *architekton*, one *δοσπρακάριος* or *ostrakarios* (tile-maker) and one *χωροβάτης* or *chorobates* (land-surveyor) are attested, while an epitaph commemorates a *μηχανοδέτης* or *mechanodotes*, a specialist who supervised the assembly or construction machines (TROMBLEY 1987, 21-22; for discussion of Korykos inscriptions, see

also PATLAGEAN 1977, 156-170 and VARINLIOĞLU 2007, 293-296).

⁹³ For a later example, cf. PRAK 2011, 398-402.

⁹⁴ ZANINI 2007, 400.

⁹⁵ As to dating, the letter is to be assigned to between AD 373, when Amphilochius was elevated to the episcopal throne of Iconium, and after AD 381, the period of Gregory’s ascendancy. See discussion and bibliography in SILVAS 2007, 198.

⁹⁶ On the role of bishops in the design and management of construction projects, cf. MARSILI 2019, 239-250.

⁹⁷ LIMBERIS 2011, 68-96.

⁹⁸ *Ibid.*, 90.

⁹⁹ KLOCK 1984, 161; on Sebasteia and the cult of the Forty Martyrs, see LIMBERIS 2011, 137-140; 2020.

¹⁰⁰ For analysis and reconstructions, cf. *ibid.*, 88-94. Centralized plans are uncommon in Anatolia, but an example is offered by the sixth-century Church 8 at Binbirkilise in Lycaonia, southeast of Iconium: its domed octagonal core, higher than the cross arms, was amplified with barrel-vaulted projections on three sides and an apse on the fourth (OUSTERHOUT 2013). In Syria, the early sixth-century church of St. George at Ezra’ shows a central octagon supporting drum and dome, with four corner niches but no extending cruciform arms (KRAU- THEIMER 1986, 139).

larger and more elaborate version of Gregory's building. Built between the end of the fourth and the early 5th c., the *martyrion* of St. Philip stood out because of its size, its exceptional plan and lavish decoration, all suggestive of an imperially sponsored project. The main building is an octagon covered by a wooden dome, expanded by deep, barrel-vaulted niches, with the four entrances built out to form a cross. The entire structure is enclosed in an ambulatory that from the outside gives the complex the appearance of a square¹⁰¹.

In addition to the general description of the *martyrion* built of «clay bricks and chance stones», Gregory details his plans for the finishing of architectural elements (lintels, columns, capitals, pedestals, and the like). This requires skilled stoneworkers who will not charge him an unreasonable amount of money for their labour. Gregory explains to Amphilochius that he had been requested an exorbitant sum («Let your truthful soul be aware that some here were negotiating with me to furnish thirty workers for a gold piece for dressed stonework – with, of course, a stipulated ration along with the gold piece») and asks his cousin to procure him suitable craftsmen («Now, as far as skill and fair dealing in the matter of wages are concerned, I know that the workers in your region are better for our need than those that can be hired here»)¹⁰².

Iconium was located at approximately km 200 from Nyssa, and, strictly speaking, the stoneworkers whom Gregory was hoping to receive could have been Lycaonians rather than Isaurians¹⁰³. Lycaonia and Isauria had however constituted a single administrative unit in the Roman period, and the two regions had long shared mutual political, cultural, and ecclesiastic relations¹⁰⁴. Hence, Isaurian identity was rather blurred and for contemporaries was neither simple nor uncontroversial¹⁰⁵.

It is nonetheless clear that the stoneworkers from the region of Iconium represented the best option available. Gregory's primary purpose is to make the decoration of the *martyrion* fits his economic constraints and to hire the best artisans for the scope without excessive financial effort.

The stonemasons' task is not only for the eight pillars, which need to be adorned with a beautiful facing, but the task also requires moulded bases on square plinths, and capitals sculpted in the Corinthian style. The porch too will be of marble finished with suitable ornament. The doorways that are placed upon them will be adorned with the kind of engravings that are customary to beautifying the moulding of the entablature. We shall of course provide the materials for all these. The form that is to be impressed on the material skill will bestow¹⁰⁶.

The forty columns of the peristyle require expert sculpting as well, but Gregory omits their specific style.

Since Gregory had restricted funds, he asked Amphilochius

to relieve us completely of anxiety concerning the workers. If the worker wants to contract with us, let a definite measure of work, as far as possible, be fixed each day, lest he pass the time idly, and subsequently, though he has no work to show for it, demands payment for having worked for us for so many days... O man of God, promise boldly as far as it is possible and lawful, that they will meet with fair dealing from us and be paid their full wages: for we shall give all and keep nothing back, in the same way that, through our prayers. God also opens to us his hand of blessing¹⁰⁷.

Gregory's stoneworkers were clearly travelling to complete a single commission, and the purpose and duration of their employment was thus the main criterion in determining remuneration. Thus, he wanted to have a clear contract of how much each worker was to do per day.

¹⁰¹ For a full discussion of the *martyrion* of St. Philip at Hierapolis, D'ANDRIA 2011/12.

¹⁰² GREG. NYSS. *Ep.* 25.12: «Πεπεισθω δὲ ἡ ἀψευδὴς σου ψυχὴ ὅτι τῶν ἐνταῦθ' αἰσθητῶν τριάκοντά μοι τεχνίτας συνέθεντο τὸν χρόνον ἐπὶ τῷ τετραπεδικῷ ἔργῳ, δηλαδὴ καὶ τῆς τετυπωμένης τροφῆς τῷ χρυσινω ἀκολουθούσης· ἡμῖν δὲ ἡ τοιαύτη τῶν λίθων <κατασκευὴ> οὐ πάρεστιν, ἀλλ' ὀστρακίνη πλίνθους ὕλη τοῦ οικοδομήματος ἔσται καὶ οἱ ἐπιτυχόντες λίθοι, ὡς μὴ εἶναι αὐτοῖς ἀνάγκη τρῖβειν τὸν χρόνον ἐν τῷ τὰ μέτωπα τῶν λίθων συγγέειν ἐναρμονίως πρὸς ἀλλήλα. Ἐγὼ δὲ κατὰ τὴν τέχνην καὶ περὶ τὸν μισθὸν εὐγνωμοσύνην ἐπίσταμαι τοὺς αὐτόθεν κρείττους εἶναι τῶν ἐνταῦθα κατεμπορευομένων τῆς χρείας ἡμῶν» (transl. SILVAS 2007, 201).

¹⁰³ MANGO 1966, 258.

¹⁰⁴ BREYTENBACH-ZIMMERMANN 2016.

¹⁰⁵ Isaurians called themselves *Cietae*, and Isaurian identity was rather an indication of belonging to the Roman province of Isauria or from a broader geographical region, an affiliation highlighted and then stressed as a result of Zeno's imperial rule (BURGESS 1990; ELTON

2000).

¹⁰⁶ GREG. NYSS. *Ep.* 25.13-14: «Τὸ δὲ τῶν λαοζῶων ἔργον οὐ μόνον ἐν τοῖς κίοσιν ἔστι τοῖς δόκῳ, οὐδὲ χρῆ ἀυτοῖς τῷ καλλωπισμῷ βελτιῶσαι, ἀλλὰ βωμοειδεῖς σπείρας ἀπαιτεῖ τὸ ἔργον καὶ καφαλίδας κατὰ τὸ Κορίνθιον εἶδος. Καὶ εἰσοδος ἐκ μαρμάρων τῷ καθήκοντι κόσμῳ κατειργασμένων, <καὶ> καθυπερκείμενα τούτων θυρώματα τοιαύταις γραφαῖς τισι, καθὼς ἔθος ἔστιν, εἰς κάλλως κατὰ τὴν τοῦ γαισίου προβολὴν ἐξηχρημένα – ὧν πάντων αἱ μὲν ὕλαι δῆλον ὅτι παρ' ἡμῶν πορισθήσονται, τὸ δὲ ἐπὶ τῇ ὕλῃ εἶδος ἡ τέχνη δώσει –, πρὸς τούτοις δὲ καὶ κατὰ τὸ περίσῳον κίονες, οὐχ ἡττους ὄντες τῶν τεσσαράκοντα, λαοζῶων ἔργον καὶ οὗτοι πάντως εἰσίν» (transl. SILVAS 2007, 201).

¹⁰⁷ GREG. NYSS. *Ep.* 25.17: «Ἀλλὰ τούτοις μὲν τι καὶ παιδιὰς καταμείκται· σὺ δὲ μοι, ὦ ἄνθρωπε τοῦ Θεοῦ, ὅπως ἂν δυνατόν καὶ νουομισμένον ἦ, οὗτο τοῖς ἀνθρώποις συνθέμενος θαρρῶν ἐπάγγελται πᾶσιν αὐτοῖς τὴν παρ' ἡμῶν εὐγνωμοσύνην καὶ τὴν τῶν μισθῶν ἀποπλήρωσιν δώσομεν γὰρ ἀνελλιπῶς τῷ τὰ πάντα, τοῦ Θεοῦ διὰ τῶν σῶν εὐχῶν καὶ ἡμῖν τὴν χεῖρα τῆς εὐλογίας ἀνοίγοντος» (transl. SILVAS 2007, 201-202).

Other interesting snippets of information about the activity of Isaurian stoneworkers are to be found in the late sixth/early seventh-century *Life of Symeon the Younger*¹⁰⁸. According to its anonymous author, Symeon received the vision of an angel marking out the shape of a monastery and a church on the Wondrous Mountain, present-day Saman Daği, km 18 S-W of Antioch, where he had already spent several years on the top of a column¹⁰⁹. Hence,

God set in motion the men of the Isaurian land and many multitudes from other places, and they kept coming to the Saint bringing their sick, men afflicted by various infirmities and tormented by unclean spirits, and all of these he cured by his word. Giving thanks to the Lord through his Saint, they laboured in the work of quarrying and constructing the monastery, setting time-limits for themselves (*ὀρίζοντες ἑαυτοῖς προθεσμίας*) and providing their own necessities. Two or three days before the appointed time-limits had been completed, other came in greater numbers... and they, too, stayed and laboured in the work that was in progress. The report of this progress. The report of this spread far and wide, and everyone came running to the blessed and cured... bringing along their own provisions and the tools they needed for such works¹¹⁰.

In the same way,

others – natives of the village of Kouvramon in the territory of Seleucia in Isauria, being afflicted by various diseases, came to the servant of God to be cured, and having obtained his blessing they remained for a few days to labour in the construction of the monastery¹¹¹.

Symeon himself supervised the construction works and tasked the Isaurians and his monks with digging cisterns and wells, and sculpting column capitals¹¹².

Isaurian stoneworkers also figure in the *Life of Saint Martha*, the mother of Symeon the Younger, who had become object of veneration herself. The early seventh-century *Life* narrates that, shortly after her death (around AD 560), Martha appeared to his son and the members of the monastic community of the Wondrous Mountain to insist that an oratory be built on the S side of the monastic complex to house her remains¹¹³. She showed the plan of the oratory and insisted that it should have three conches, one toward the E, and to smaller apses on the sides¹¹⁴. The brethren urged Symeon to start work on the building, but the saint replied that

if this is pleasing to Him, He will assemble once again, through the Holy Spirit, masons from the land of Isauria... And on the holy day of the Lord [Sunday] God's servant Symeon... directed that [the outlines] the triconch chapel be traced in accordance with the form that had been delineated by the Blessed Woman and shown to him. And while they were tracing it, lo, there assembled a throng of masons from the land of Isauria and other places, men afflicted by various diseases and infirmities, who, after, coming before the saint, asked to be allowed to do the work¹¹⁵.

On a superficial reading of these texts, we might assume that the Isaurians came to the Wondrous Mountain as pilgrims in the hope of being cured of their infirmities. Another passage of the *Life of Symeon*

¹⁰⁸ For the chronology of composition of the *Life of Symeon the Younger*, see PARKER 2022, 15-21.

¹⁰⁹ *Vita S. Symeoni Iunioris* 95. Partly carved in the bedrock, the monastery consisted of a rectangular precinct, three churches and related structures, all arranged around Symeon's pillar (*megas stylos*) in the central octagon. The monastery also possessed a baptistery, several hospices, and a bathhouse: DJOBADZE 1986.

¹¹⁰ *Vita S. Symeoni Iunioris* 96: «Καὶ τοῦτου γενομένου, ἐκίνησεν ὁ Θεὸς τοὺς ἀνθρώπους τῆς τῶν Ἰσαύρων χώρας καὶ ἄλλων δὲ τόπων πλήθη πολλὰ, καὶ ἤρχοντο πρὸς τὸν ἅγιον φέροντες ἀσθενοῦντας καὶ ποικίλοις πάσθει συνεχομένους καὶ ὑπὸ πνευμάτων ἀκαθάρτων ἐνοχλουμένους, καὶ πάντας λόγῳ ἐθεράπευσεν, καὶ εὐχαριστοῦντες τῷ Κυρίῳ διὰ τοῦ ἁγίου ἔκαμνον εἰς τὸ λατομεῖον καὶ εἰς τὴν μονῆς, ὀρίζοντες ἑαυτοῖς προθεσμίας καὶ τὰς δαπάνας ἑαυτοῖς κομίζοντες. Πρὸ δύο δὲ ἡμερῶν τοῦ πληρωθῆναι τὰς ὀρισθείσας παρ' ἐκείνοις προθεσμίας, ἄλλοι πλείονες ἐφίσταντο ... καὶ ἔμενον καὶ αὐτοὶ κάμνοντες ἐν τῷ γινόμενῳ ἔργῳ. Λοιπὸν δὲ διεδόθη τοῦτο πανταχοῦ, καὶ πάντες προσέτρεχον εὐλογοῦντες καὶ ἰαθῆναι ἐκ τῶν συνεχοῦσάν αὐτοὺς ἀσθεσιῶν καὶ ἐργάζεσθαι ἐν τῷ ἔργῳ, φέροντες μεθ' ἑαυτῶν τὰς ἰδίας δαπάνας καὶ τὰ ἐργαλεῖα ὧντερ ἐρχίζον ἐν τῷ τοιοῦτῳ ἔργῳ» (transl. MANGO 1966, 359-360).

¹¹¹ *Vita S. Symeoni Iunioris* 192: «Ἄλλοι πάλιν ἀπὸ Κουβραμῶν χωρίου ὀρμώμενοι ἐνορίας Σελευκείας τῆς Ἰσαυρίας διαφόροις πάσθει κρατοῦμενοι

ἦλθον πρὸς τὸν δούλον τοῦ Θεοῦ τοῦ ἰαθῆναι, καὶ λαβόντες τὴν χάριν παρέμειναν ἡμέρας τινὰς κοπιῶντες ἐν ταῖς οἰκοδομαῖς τῆς μονῆς» (transl. MANGO 1966, 360).

¹¹² *Vita S. Symeoni Iunioris* 108. The anonymous author portrays Symeon as a master builder who ensures the efficiency of manpower: thus, the octagon and the pillar, the very heart of the monastery on the Wondrous Mountain, were completed only after 10 years of labour and were dedicated on 4 June AD 551 (SCHACHNER 2010, 361).

¹¹³ Unfortunately, there is no secure evidence to provide a precise chronology for the *Life*. However, its author undoubtedly knew the *Life of Symeon the Younger*, dating from the late 6th and early 7th c., and details fit a seventh-century date of composition (PARKER 2022, 169-170).

¹¹⁴ *Vita S. Marthae m. Sym. Styl. iun.* 46: «...σκάριφον ὑποδεικνύουσα τρεῖς κόγχας ἔχοντος, μίαν κατὰ ἀνατολᾶς καὶ ἑτέραν ἐκ δεξιῶν καὶ ἄλλην ἐξ εὐωνύμων». See VAN DEN VEN 1961.

¹¹⁵ *Vita S. Marthae m. Sym. Styl. iun.* 49: «ἰδοὺ τρεῖς τοῦτο καὶ τετράκις παραμένονεν ἡ κυρία ἡ μεγάλη ... εὐκτηρίου τε σκάριφον ὑποδεικνύουσα τρεῖς κόγχας ἔχοντος, μίαν κατὰ ἀνατολᾶς καὶ ἑτέραν ἐκ δεξιῶν, καὶ ἄλλην ἐξ εὐωνύμων, καὶ τὴν δλημ τῆς οἰκοδομῆς διαγραφὴν ὑποδηλοῦσα καὶ παρεγγῶσα μοι πᾶσιν ὑμῖν ἀπαγγεῖλαι τοῦτο· ἐμοῦ δὲ παραιτούμενου τοῦτο εἰπεῖν, ἀγανακτεῖν ἀπεφῆγναι κατ' ἐμοῦ· ἀκριβῶς οὖν ὑμῖν τὰ παρ' αὐτῆς σημαίνω» (transl. MANGO 1972, 126-127).

the Younger sets us, however on the right way. «Close to the city of Antioch, at the place called Apatê, there was a workshop of Isaurians who were cutting stone and constructing the walls». The Isaurians brought to Symeon one of their companions who had fell ill. Symeon asked the young man, a pagan, to anathemise the idols to be cured. However, he refused and was taken back to his own country, where he was healed only three years later¹¹⁶.

Hence, the Isaurians went to Syria not as pilgrims bringing their tools and providing for their own expenses, but as stoneworkers¹¹⁷. By emphasising the labour of devotees, the *Life of Symeon the Younger* portrays construction as a ritualised performance of thanksgiving to the saint and membership in the monastic community¹¹⁸. But, in reality, the Isaurians went to the Wondrous Mountain in great numbers, perhaps on a seasonal basis¹¹⁹.

Like Constantinopolitan carvers, Isaurians moved to pursue employment opportunities. However, Isaurian stoneworkers did not only rely imperial building patronage but moved on a trans-regional level wherever their skills and expertise were required. Gregory of Nyssa's *Letter 25* attests, nonetheless, that written contracts were made for commissions outsourced to "Isaurian" freelance craftsmen.

Even though it is often difficult, if not impossible to distinguish among different patterns of migration and mobility, the movements of Isaurian stoneworkers can be referred to as "circular migration". According to Tilly's categorisation, this takes a social unit through a set of arrangements which returns it to the origin in the short- or medium-term. Because "circular migration" commonly rests on the maintenance of households in the area of origin, it rarely moves whole families and often draws disproportionately on one sex¹²⁰. Isaurian workshops, most likely composed exclusively of men, moved to satisfy the labour requirements of specific building projects. Although this means that they did not benefit from the security of a fixed income, they arguably enjoyed great flexibility and freedom, able to accept commissions from a wide range of patrons. This also means that they were aware of the possibilities that the labour market offered them at destination, and this knowledge must have depended on established and reliable networks for information. Reputation was a prime factor, and Isaurians were famous for their skills in building and stone working and were clearly sought for their services abroad¹²¹.

«...MARKIANOS KYRIS, TECHNITES ...MADE THIS»: MOBILE BUILDERS AND STONEMEN ON THE LIMESTONE MASSIF OF NORTHEASTERN SYRIA

Stone working on the Limestone Massif of northeast Syria offers a useful complement to Constantinopolitan and Isaurian study-cases, not least because we can explore a rather different deployment of stoneworkers and stone working skills. It provides a useful standpoint for the study of a craft tradition largely distinct from State and Church-organised and more thoroughly institutionalised enterprises.

The Limestone Massif forms an almost unbroken series of ranges (the Jebel Siman/Halaqa in the north; the Jebel Barisha/A'la/Wastani above the Orontes; and the Jebel Zawiye in the S) standing roughly between 400 and 800 above sea level and stretching between the Antioch and Aleppo. What is today a barren belt of low karstic hill, supported a thriving countryside and prosperous rural communities in Late Antiquity. The area preserves the remains of some seven hundred villages, dating primarily from the mid-4th to the mid-7th c. First described by the French architect M. de Vogüé, these settlements, known as "The Dead Cities", were made famous in the 1950s by the publications of G. Tchalenko and then were extensively studied by J.-P. Sodini and G. Tate¹²².

¹¹⁶ *Vita S. Symeoni Iunioris* 188: «Πλησίον τῆς Ἀντιοχείας εἰς τὴν λεγομένην Ἀπάτην ἦν ἐργαστήριον Ἰσαύρων λατομοῦντων καὶ οἰκοδομοῦντων ἐν τῷ τείχει. Εἰς δὲ τις νεώτερος ἐξ αὐτῶν ἀπῆλθεν ἄραι ξύλα ἀπὸ ἀλσώδους διαφέροντος ἑλληγίζοντι χωρίῳ καλουμένῳ Πουλίωνος ὑπῆρχε δὲ καὶ αὐτὸς τῆς αὐτῆς τῶν μουσαρῶν Ἑλλήνων θρησκείας. Ὡς δὲ ταῦτα μετὰ ἀδιακρίσεως ἤρεν, κυριευθεὶς ὑπὸ δαίμονος παραχρήμα παρελύθη ὄλος, ὥστε μηδὲν τῶν μελῶν αὐτοῦ δύνασθαι κινεῖν» (transl. MANGO 1966, 361).

¹¹⁷ *Ibid.*

¹¹⁸ BOERO 2022, 253.

¹¹⁹ Besides the *Lives* of Symeon the Younger and Martha, a third important hagiographic reference to Isaurians as master builders comes from Cyril of Scythopolis, according to whom two Isaurian architects,

Gelasios and Theodoulos, built the Great Laura founded by saint Sabas in AD 478 on the cliffs of the Kidron Gorge (Wadi en-Nar) between Jerusalem and the Dead Sea (MANGO 1966, 349).

¹²⁰ TILLY 1978, 52-53; 1990, 88-80.

¹²¹ The fact that in the parallel passages of Theophanes and Malalas on the collapse of the dome of Hagia Sophia the name of Isaurians is preceded by the definite article but is not given any further qualification («ἐργαζομένων τῶν Ἰσαύρων») implies that Isaurians were known as the construction workers *par excellence* (MANGO 1966, 359).

¹²² DE VOGÜÉ 1865-1877; TCHALENKO 1953-1959; SODINI *et alii* 1980; TATE 1992. Useful overviews are FOSS 1997, 197-204 and 226-229; TROMBLEY 2004 and DECKER 2009, 33-44.

This research has sparked a debate concerning the economic base of the late antique prosperity of the region. Tchalenko argued that, especially from the 5th c. onwards, the wealth of the Limestone Massif derived from an intense olive monoculture sustained by the fiscal demands of the *annona* and the exportation of oil from the ports of the Syrian coast¹²³. Recent work has undermined some of Tchalenko's propositions, however. Excavations at the village of Dhs proved that oil production was important, but stock-raising was equally significant, with arable agriculture (wheat, legumes), practised in pockets of fertile soils, and viticulture and arboriculture¹²⁴. In the light of this evidence, the Limestone Massif appears now as part of a more typical Mediterranean mixed agriculture regime. Its inhabitants did not rely exclusively on oil as a cash-crop for exportation, because for peasants to depend on the market for their own food was not something that the late antique economy, however sophisticated it was, could sustain. Hence the evidence for a mixed economy in the area¹²⁵.

The wealth of the Limestone Massif's communities found expression in the construction of well-built and comfortable houses, which show little differentiation between them except for the number of rooms they had on each floor (from one to thirteen, though 86 per cent had four or less)¹²⁶.

Libanius and Theodoret of Cyrus refer both to villages with peasant owners and villages with a single extended owner in Antioch's hinterland¹²⁷. Still, the general homogeneity of houses argues against large-scale landowning and suggests that they were used for lodging peasant families and as centres of agricultural exploitation. The inhabitants of the Limestone Massif were primarily medium- and small-scale landowners, tenants, and seasonal labourers¹²⁸. As Chris Wickham observes, «it would be hard to argue that peasants would have enough surplus left to pay for them after not only tax but rent as well, and even less credible that landlords should put up the money»¹²⁹.

The villages of the Limestone Massif appeared exceptional until thirty years ago, but it is now clear they were not. Similar, if less spectacularly preserved villages are known from other semi-arid regions of the Levant (Cilicia, Hawran and the Negev) and of northern Africa, and they all display high levels of prosperity¹³⁰. There is currently consensus among historians and archaeologists about the fact that this prosperity was based on hundreds of thousands of peasant consumers and producers¹³¹. Late antique peasants were able to afford goods, buildings, professional services and even luxuries on a scale not attested before. Leslie Dossey, in her recent survey of peasantry in Roman Africa, has argued for a late antique "consumer revolution"¹³².

As said, stone architecture was undoubtedly one of the main, if not the main area of investment by peasant households, and the growing wealth of the villagers of the Limestone Massif of Syria is shown by changes in house construction.

Fourth-century houses at Sergilla were simple one-storeyed buildings with living and service quarters organised around an ample courtyard, usually covering the 50 per cent of the surface of the whole complex (on average ca. 200 square meters). These houses were built in *opus africanum*, with large orthostats and smaller infill between them, or in other mixed building techniques¹³³. In the 5th and 6th c. the courtyard houses of the Limestone Massif develop into ampler structures: two-storeyed buildings, ranging in size between 300 and 600 square meters, make their appearance (Fig. 6). The ground floor was generally reserved for agricultural activities and stables. Living activities were, meanwhile, concentrated on the upper storey, which was clearly distinct from the service area, while subsidiary buildings (kitchens, sheds, storerooms) clustered around the main building. External walls and faades were enlivened by columned porticoes and balconies, arched niches, and multiple windows. All these elements, alongside the use of perfectly squared blocks and a

¹²³ TCHALENKO 1953-1959, 433-436.

¹²⁴ *Ibid.*, 281-284.

¹²⁵ WICKHAM 2005, 445. It is worth noting that the Limestone Massif was part of the north-eastern quadrant of the Mediterranean that, centred on Antioch and its hinterland, Cilicia and Cyprus, was the main area of production of LR1 amphorae, mainly used for the transport of oil: DECKER 2001, 76-77.

¹²⁶ TATE 1992, 15-188, 257-265.

¹²⁷ DECKER 2009, 70-71. The Limestone Massif contains very few buildings that could be classified as villa-estates or grand houses, such as we might expect had there been great patrons or owners living on the land, though the question of absentee landlords remains. It is likely, however, that estates were to be located in the more fertile lowlands than the marginal limestone hills (BAVANT 2013).

¹²⁸ TATE 1992, 257-271; see also WICKHAM 2005, 443-448.

¹²⁹ *Ibid.*, 447.

¹³⁰ See for a recent summary JACOBS 2020a.

¹³¹ The vast scholarship on peasant economy is usefully summarized in WHITTOW 2010, 146-160; for a later period, cf. WICKHAM 2023, 663-688. For a useful discussion of the term "peasant", see GREY 2011, 26-33.

¹³² DOSSEY 2010, 62-97. The ceramic assemblages from Dhs comprise, for example, sixth- and seventh-century Phocaean Red Slip fine ware and LRA3 amphorae of Aegean origin, alongside local imitations of African Red Slip, Phocaean Red Slip, Late Roman D and Brittle Ware (VOKAER 2010), while a hundred copper coins are a substantial number for a rural site (SODINI *et alii* 1980, 267-287).

¹³³ DUVETTE 2018, 82-83.

Fig. 6. Serğilla: Maison 08, filot 11 (photo A.).

luxurious sculpted decoration, are suggestive of the work of teams of specialised stoneworkers, using bollards and cranes and displaying considerable experience in stone working and sculpture¹³⁴.

The presence of specialised workers as stonecutters and sculptors poses the thorny question of non-agricultural economic activity in the villages of the Limestone Massif.

In his *Oration in Praise of Antioch* (AD 356), Libanius mentions the existence of

large and populous villages with a larger population than many towns; they have a mutual intercourse through their festivals, to attend which each one in turn issues and receives invitations: their relaxations, pleasures and hopes are identical; they allow others to share in their abundance, and make up their deficiencies from them¹³⁵.

This passage fits with the definition by G. Dagron of the greater villages of the late antique Levant as settlements with city-like institutions and economic structures, but without city-rights. According to Dagron, most villages consisted almost entirely of (free) peasants, and so lacked the variety of occupations that was so essential to a city, but traders and craftsmen might have been present and create a community with urban qualities. These villages were, thus, mostly embedded in local trade, agriculture, and manufacturing networks, though also indirectly connected to the wider and more cosmopolitan world of cities¹³⁶.

Archaeological and epigraphic evidence present, however, a somewhat less straightforward picture. Except for churches and half-a-dozen baths, public structures such as markets, hostels and storehouses cannot be easily recognized, and shops and workshops are equally elusive¹³⁷. Thus, the Limestone Massif villages seem to have been almost entirely devoted to farming and to have had comparatively little artisanal activity, with the notable exception of the building trades¹³⁸. In the small area of the Limestone Massif,

¹³⁴ DUVETTE 2018, 83-89.

¹³⁵ LIB. *Or.* 11.230: «...κάμει μεγάλοι καὶ πολυάνθρωποι πόλεων οὐκ ὀλίγων πλέον πολυανδρούμενοι καὶ χειροτέχναις ὥσπερ ἐν ἄστεσι χρώμενοι, κοινούμενοι πρὸς ἀλλήλας <τὰ> σφῶναυτῶν διὰ τῶν παηγύρεων καλυθαί τε ἐν μέρει παρ' αὐτὴν ἐκάστη καὶ καλούμενοι καὶ τοῖς εὐθυμούμανεῖ τε καὶ χαρίζομενοι καὶ κερδαίνουσαι» (transl. NORMAN 2000, 54).

¹³⁶ DAGRON 1979.

¹³⁷ However, we cannot rule out the possibility that periodic markets were held in open spaces, where stalls and tents could be erected for

the accommodation of the sellers and the goods on sale (TATE 1992, 108-115, 253-258).

¹³⁸ *Ibid.*, 287-289. A similar picture can be sketched for Egypt, where the rich papyrological documentation gives an unparalleled insight into the economy of the region. According to Peter van Minnen, the place of craft and trade activities within the village economy conformed to the general pattern of the subsistence economy in general: everything was made for direct use in the community itself, and what could not be made there was acquired by exchange with neighbouring villages (VAN MINNEN 1987, 72-81; similar conclusions in BAGNALL 2005, 556-573).

Fig. 7. Btirsra (Serġilla): sample-books carved on the wall of the so-called “Maison de Sculpteur” (after DE VOGÜÉ 1865-1877).

nearly 40 inscriptions have yielded a series of named builders (*oikodomoï* and *technitai*) working there between the 3rd and the 6th c. (AD 224-225 to AD 549-550)¹³⁹. Moreover, the walls of the ground-floor excavated in the rock-bed of the so-called “Maison de Sculpteur” at the village of Btirsra, nearby Serġilla, bear a series of carved ornamental motifs, a sort of sample-book available for customers to choose from and place orders to the owner of the house, who may have been a sculptor¹⁴⁰ (Fig. 7).

The best-known example is that of the *τεχνίτης* Markianos Kyris, who was a permanent resident in the village of Bābisqā, but supervised the construction of several churches at Darqitā, Bābisqā, Bā’ūde, Ksēgbe e Qasr el Banāt, all situated in close proximity to each other on the Jebel Barisha, within a distance of ca. 10 kilometres¹⁴¹. Epigraphic evidence allows to follow the activity of Markianos and his workshop over about thirty years between the end of the 4th and the early decades of the 5th c.¹⁴²

An inscription from Bābisqā remembers Markianos as a presbyter, and his works betrays a good knowledge of arithmetic and geometry¹⁴³. In fact, it would seem logical to suggest that Markianos had at some point in his life been educated in Antioch both in his professions, that of presbyter and that of *technites*¹⁴⁴. For sure, his activity was marked by a series of innovation in building technology and church decoration: sculpted friezes, acanthus and palmettes on cornices, as well as similarly decorated capitals make their appearance in the cult buildings erected by Markianos and his workshop¹⁴⁵.

Two other professional stoneworkers, Julianos and his brother Marinos, were active roughly in the same period as Markianos himself at Brād and Bābisqā¹⁴⁶, confirming the high demand for skilled masons¹⁴⁷.

¹³⁹ TATE 1991, 74-76.

¹⁴⁰ DE VOGÜÉ 1865-1877, pls. 43 and 47; TATE 1992, 298-299.

¹⁴¹ Local workshops – most likely made up of local individuals whose main occupation was farming – are also attested in the middle Byzantine period. For example, in eleventh-century Mani the *marmararios* Niketas decorated several churches in villages located within a radius of approximately 20 kilometres (ΔΡΑΝΔΑΚΗΣ 1972; 1975/76; see also VANDERHEYDE 1998, 767-769).

¹⁴² MILSON 2003, 160-164.

¹⁴³ *Ibid.*, 165-180.

¹⁴⁴ BAVANT 2013, 40-41. In Late Antiquity it was common for ecclesiastics to practice second professions and trades (WIŚNIEWSKI 2021). A fifth/sixth century inscription from Olympia (IvO 657) mentions, for example, a reader (*ἀναγνώστης*) who also was a marble-worker (*μαρμαράριος*).

¹⁴⁵ STRUBE 1993, 66-67.

¹⁴⁶ Interestingly, Julianos is recorded in several inscriptions as *ἀρχιτέκτων*, *τεχνίτης*, and *οικοδόμος*, all belonging to the Church of Julianos at Brād dated to AD 399-402 and suggesting the interchangeability of the terms. Marinos is probably identical with the homonymous *τεχνίτης* from Bābisqā (*ibid.*, 53-57).

¹⁴⁷ This trend was gradually reversed after the mid-6th c., after which there is no evidence for further construction. Nonetheless, people still lived in the Limestone Massif (at Dehes, pottery shows occupation through the Umayyad and Abbasid period), and activity continued, but of a different order. The area played a much more localized economic role, only producing oil for the still prosperous inland cities of Aleppo and Qinnasrīn (former Beroia and Chalcis). Only in the later centuries the Limestone Massif villages were emptied altogether, perhaps during the tenth- and eleventh-century frontier wars between Byzantium and the Seljuks (SODINI *et alii* 1980, 234-264; TATE 1992, 367-376).

A significant share of this demand was possibly sustained by communal building enterprises, as the construction of village churches¹⁴⁸. A Syriac inscription from a church in Ḥirbat Ḥasan documents the collective gifts that supported its construction: «In the year 556 according to the era of Antioch [= AD 507/508], this church was completed. And there were spent of darics, 85; and of beans, wheat, and lentils, 430 bushels; besides the chief expenses»¹⁴⁹.

Building projects and their funding could cement communal relationships (voluntary workers from the villagers could also take part in the construction of churches alongside hired builders)¹⁵⁰, and not only the construction of buildings and gifts to churches allowed donors to express their identity, both individual and communal, but they also bore religious significance¹⁵¹. This is confirmed by a different category of church donations: that of liturgical silver plate. A good example is the sixth-to-seventh treasure from Kaper Koraon (Kurin near Stuma, Aleppo), mostly made up by objects of modest monetary value (from ca. half a *solidus* for a silver spoon to ca. four *solidi* for a chalice), comparable to the estimated costs of smaller mosaic panels¹⁵². This hints to moderately prosperous or “middle-class” donors, like those who contributed to the funding of churches, among whom – it is worth noting – also were the *architekton* Julianos and the *technitai* Marinios and Markianos¹⁵³.

The activity of the stonemasons and stoneworkers of the Limestone Massif was deeply embedded in the social and economic fabric of the region. Stone working was a seasonal activity and was complementary with other occupations¹⁵⁴. Seasonality is a key factor to the agricultural cycle and to building works as well¹⁵⁵. Although ancient agriculture was a year-round activity, there were certain phases which were particularly work intensive: for example, wheat and olives, the main crops of the Limestone Massif, were harvested in May/June and October/November respectively. In the same way, building projects were not equally distributed throughout the year, and the working season of the building trades generally lasted from late spring to autumn¹⁵⁶.

Being season and project driven, the activity of the master builders and the stoneworkers of the Limestone Massif did not differ from that of the Isaurians. But, in comparison to the latter, they moved over very short distances, usually to or from other villages in the immediate vicinity. According to Tilly's typology, they can be classified as “local migrants”, who moved to a geographical contiguous market in labour, and their movements involved no or minimal break with the place of origin¹⁵⁷.

In conclusion, both written and archaeological evidence can be meaningfully employed to analyse skilled labour mobility in the early Byzantine empire from a qualitative and typological angle. The same evidence can be explored to investigate other aspects, such as the socio-economic status of early Byzantine stone workers and their identity.

¹⁴⁸ A similar development has been recognized in other regions of the Levant as well. In Cilicia, an inscription dated to AD 590 from Çemkale celebrates the construction of a church in honour of the Theotokos by the villagers of Sipa under the supervision of the *ergolabos* Stephanos (DAGRON-FEISSEL 1987, 192-193). In the Tur 'Abdin, a late inscription (from AD 752 to 755) commemorates villagers who made monetary contributions to the construction of the church of the Monastery of Mar Jacob the Recluse at Şalah. In Jordan, there are a few references to communal donations: the church of St Theodore in the neighbourhood of Bosra was built in the second half of the 6th c. by the local community, while the inscription at Khirbat aṭ-Ṭaṭṭūr (Dayr al-Musmār) describes how the mosaics of the church of Kaloa was completed thanks to the effort of Presbyter Giobb and the local community in AD 622/623 (HAMARNEH 2010, 65). A mosaic inscription dated to AD 627 from the church of St George at Khirbat al-Samra is a prayer for the souls and safety of the entire village (JACOBS 2020b, 42).

¹⁴⁹ LITTMANN 1904, 15-21. A second Syriac inscription of unknown provenance, dated to the fall of AD 504, grants tranquillity to God's monasteries and churches and offers «good payment to everyone who laboured and to him who stretched forth a hand for our Lord» (STEINER 1990).

¹⁵⁰ A later example can be found in the *Life of Saint Nikon the Metanoite*, which narrates that in tenth-century Sparta voluntary workers from among the townspeople, as well as professional builders, worked on the construction of the church of St Photeine under the supervision of saint Nikon, who assumed both the role master mason and contractor (OUSTERHOUT 1999, 53). Moreover, the number of specialists necessary for the construction of the Çanlı Kilise, an eleventh-century masonry church in Anatolia, has been estimated at just 3 persons, while unskilled labour required a minimum of 10 persons per

season: PICKETT forth.

¹⁵¹ On the importance of communal gifts to churches in village society, cf. BOERO 2022, 255-262.

¹⁵² The treasure consists of some fifty-six chalices, patens, crosses, lamps, flasks, and other silver objects, for a total weight of about 83 lbs. These items were donated to a church of St George by about fifty individuals, only one of whom was an ecclesiastic. Most of donors were merchants, artisans, and owners of small properties, belonging to four or five families who bestowed gifts to a village church over the course of a century or so between ca. AD 540 and ca. AD 640 (MUNDELL MANGO 1986, 8-13; see also JACOBS 2020b, 39).

¹⁵³ STRUBE 1993, 53-54. On “middle class” donors, see KITZINGER 1992.

¹⁵⁴ TATE 1992, 289-290. This finds confirmation in the ethnoarchaeological studies carried out in Syria, where in the 1990s the gypsum quarries at Aramel, in the Jebel Simam, were still exploited according to traditional methods. The local population of the region, mainly engaged in farming and stock-raising, practiced extraction during the winter season (BESSAC *et alii* 1997, 188-189).

¹⁵⁵ In general, on the importance of seasonality in ancient economy, see HAWKINS 2016, 22-65.

¹⁵⁶ On the seasonality of building works, DELAINE 1997; ERDKAMP 2016, 36-41; LICHTENBERGER-RAJA 2021, 16-17. A good example in this regard is furnished by the building yard of Westminster Abbey where, in the summer months of 1253, up to 130 stonemasons and 220 assistants were working on, but this number halved by September of the same year, mainly because the assistants left the site, presumably to participate in the harvest (PRAK 2011, 386).

¹⁵⁷ TILLY 1978, 51-52.

«...ΕΚ ΤΟΥ ΕΡΓΟΧΕΙΡΟΥ ΑΥΤΟΥ ΗΜΕΡΟΥΣΙΟΝ ΕΝΟΣ ΚΕΡΑΤΙΟΥ»: WAGES AND SOCIO-ECONOMIC STATUS

Ancient historians have revalued the importance of wage labour since the 1980s. Rome was an agrarian empire and the bulk of its rural workers were subsistence farmers. Yet, the expansion of wage labour was a striking feature of the late antique eastern Mediterranean¹⁵⁸. A great share of wage labourers was employed in the building industry, the main sector of the Roman economy after primary production¹⁵⁹. Not by coincidence, builders are the workers whose wages are often preserved from a variety of sources, confirming that building labour and builders themselves were essential to the urban economies of the late antique period.

Except for Diocletian's Price Edict of AD 301, the single most promising document on the subject¹⁶⁰, our sources (papyri, *ostraca*, inscriptions, and literary sources) shed very little light on wages and prices in Late Antiquity. In the case of builders and stoneworkers the category comprised a great variety of skills and a correspondingly wide range of rates. This lack of precision in the terminology of the documents precludes identification of the specific nature of the work being paid for, and it is therefore impossible to draw up a schedule of retributions for tasks or skills. However, despite their shortcomings, these sources are often sufficient to support rough estimates of real wages. Here, we present a survey of pertinent data to gain an idea of the average craftsmen's salary in the building industry.

In Antiquity, building contracts normally fell under the rubric of *locatio-conductio*, which shows a variety of arrangements for remuneration. Labourers could be paid per period worked, per quantity of goods delivered, per tasks performed. Moreover, specific jobs could be remunerated in more than one form¹⁶¹.

In Antiquity daily wages were «the way in which [remunerations] were commonly expressed (and paid)», to quote Richard Duncan-Jones¹⁶². According to Diocletian's Price Edict, a skilled stonemason (λιθουργός τεχνίτης) and marble-carver (μαρμάριος) earned respectively 50 and 60 *denarii* per day plus a food allowance (*pastus*) of ca. 11 *denarii*, twice the daily wage of an unskilled worker, earning 25 *denarii* per day plus *pastus*¹⁶³. This skilled premium is consistent with our papyrological evidence¹⁶⁴. Evidence for daily wages is provided by literary sources as well. The *Chronicle* of Pseudo-Zachariah reports that the craftsmen and workers hired for the construction of Dara in Mesopotamia at the time of Anastasius (AD 491-518) were paid four *keratia* per day, and if they had an ass with them, eight *keratia*¹⁶⁵. Daniel of Skete tells the story of Eulogios, a quarryman from the Thebaid, whose daily wage was one *keration*¹⁶⁶.

Sources also record pieceworkers, whose retribution depended on the number of items completed¹⁶⁷. In his letter to Amphilochius, Gregory of Nyssa proposes that carvers from the Iconium region be paid for the work done and not on a daily rate basis to optimise the time and construction cost of his *martyrion*. A papyrus from Oxyrhynchos, dated to AD 569, is an acknowledgment given to Fl. Apion by Ioannis, chief of the stonemasons (κεφαλ(ή) τῶν λαοτόμων), for the receipt of one *solidus*, for which sum he engages to transport 200 great blocks of stone (λίθους μεγάλους) to a cistern (εἰς τὸν λάκκον) on Fl. Apion's estate¹⁶⁸. Another papyrus from Oxyrhynchos, dating between the late 6th and the early 7th c., contains a list of all the items provided by the λαοξόος Phileas for the repair of the church of St Philoxenos. The λαοξόος mentions a total of at least 5524 blocks for the walls, counted in batches of 50, as well as 120 capitals and 120 bases¹⁶⁹.

¹⁵⁸ KEHOE 2012, 123-125; BANAJI 2001, 190-212; FREU 2022.

¹⁵⁹ In general, construction played a significant role within any pre-modern economy as it represents one of the greatest single concentrations of labour, and its output a highly valuable product (ERDKAMP 2012; BERNARD 2017, 62).

¹⁶⁰ GROEN-VALLINGA - TACOMA 2017, 104.

¹⁶¹ *Ibid.*, 115-117. The evidence for *locatio-conductio* contract is usefully assembled by MARTIN 1989.

¹⁶² DUNCAN-JONES 1978, 160.

¹⁶³ GIACCHERO 1974, 7.2 and 5 (*de mercedibus operariorum*). That in imperial Rome construction workers were paid on a daily basis is demonstrated by the graffiti from the Baths of Trajan in Rome recording the days of work of single masons and teams over several months (VOLPE 2015).

¹⁶⁴ BERNARD 2017, 80-83. In Roman Egypt, skilled workers could command a skilled premium somewhere on the order of two or three times the wages earned by unskilled workers, especially in urban contexts (RATHBONE 2009, 314-321; FREU 2022, 156-160).

¹⁶⁵ GREATREX *et alii* 2011, 249.

¹⁶⁶ *Vita S. Danielis Sketensis*: «Ὁὗτος ὁ γέρων Εὐλόγιος λέγεται τὴν

τέχνην δὲ ἔχει λατόμου καταλύει δὲ ἐκ τοῦ ἐργοχείρου αὐτοῦ ἡμερούσιον ἐνὸς κερατίου, ἕως ἑσπέρας μηδὲν γευόμενος». See MAGOULIAS 1976, 15, and PATLAGEAN 1977, 388-389 for other evidence.

¹⁶⁷ It is also clear from the Sardis inscription of AD 459 that in late antique Asia Minor building projects were managed giving out the work to groups of free workmen, who contracted to carry out part of the construction work as long as the employer was ready to furnish "the wages mutually agreed upon" (GARNSEY 1998, 81-82; DI BRANCO 2000, 190-191).

¹⁶⁸ FREU 2022, 162.

¹⁶⁹ The papyrus makes no reference to column-shafts, which must have been made and delivered by another stonemason specialised in their production (PAPACONSTANTINO 2005). The instances of piecework display an awareness of building procedures: in Late Antiquity architects simply defined the general arrangement and important dimensions of the building before the construction process began and did not go into any details concerning finishing and decoration, except for the main architectural members (columns, capitals, and bases), as well as other large stonework (cornices, lintels), which required specialised and expensive workers. A similar procedure is attested in the above-mentioned letter by Gregory of Nyssa on the construction of a *martyrion* (*Ead.* 2007, 35-36).

Masons' marks may have been part of this piecework system, in which carvers working on a large and highly ornate building could be divided into teams assigned to zones of a monument. As suggested by evidence from late Medieval Europe, the marks informed the patron and/or the paymaster of the output of the individual masons and teams working on a project¹⁷⁰. This also fits with the organisation of the building of Hagia Sophia as described in the *Narration on Hagia Sophia*. The *τεχνίται μαίστρορες* mentioned in the text may have functioned as general managers, checking on the contractual obligations of each crew and their payment for the work done¹⁷¹.

While the available data do not allow any far-reaching conclusion, in the early Byzantine period skilled builders' wages were high, and a skilled worker who found full annual employment (here taken as a 250-day year) at these rates was moderately prosperous¹⁷². This notwithstanding the fact that – with seasonal cycles of employment, the *ad hoc* mobilization of labour and short duration of typical projects, and the sporadic nature of input at larger ones – their chances of being periodically unemployed, at least for brief periods, were high. In Antiquity, as in other preindustrial economies, the wage rates of construction workers were subject to a seasonal fluctuation between summer highs and winter lows¹⁷³.

According to Pseudo-Zachariah, the craftsmen's annual wage at Dara amounted to approximately between 41 and 82 *solidi*. The chronicler undoubtedly overinflated numbers, but these sums, exorbitant as they are, should be placed against the enormous effort taken by Anastasius, in terms of money and expertise, to turn the small village of Dara into a large and well-provided city, the fulcrum of the Roman position in Mesopotamia¹⁷⁴. Moreover, as stated in the *Narration on Hagia Sophia*, Justinian awarded bonuses to the workforce of the Great Church «so they would not lose heart»¹⁷⁵.

If these figures are not entirely reliable, they show nonetheless that skilled craftsmen, far from being destitute, were on the contrary relatively well-off individuals. Daniel of Skete affirms that with his daily salary of 1 *keration* the quarryman Eulogios was able to indulge himself in works of charity, besides paying the rent for his home located on an estate¹⁷⁶. In the *Life of Symeon the Younger*, an *οικοδόμος* with one blind eye came to the saint and asked him help to recover a small fortune of 12 *solidi* which had been stolen to him. Symeon not only restored the money, but also healed his eye and told the man that this was a more valuable gift than gold¹⁷⁷.

Against this background, the daily wage of 1/30 of a *solidus* per man demanded by the local stone-carvers from Gregory of Nyssa, and considered by him to be exorbitant, appear in line with what can be deduced from other sources. The proposed rate would have amounted, assuming a steady employment, to a yearly income of about 10 *solidi*¹⁷⁸.

High wage premiums for skilled workers offers one explanation for these wage rates, which can be compared to some historical data from Antiquity and the Middle Ages, where premia of 100 or 200 were not uncommon¹⁷⁹. This reflects the favourable employment opportunities open to those in the building trade in the early Byzantine Mediterranean, where in the 5th and 6th centuries several cities and religious sites experienced considerable building activity and various agents (the Church, the State, the aristocracy and the “middle class”) left their imprint on the urban landscape¹⁸⁰. Under these circumstances¹⁸¹, demand for skilled workers was undoubtedly high and created advantageous condition for them, as suggested by the Sardis inscription of AD 459¹⁸².

¹⁷⁰ Many different interpretations have been offered for the significance of these marks, which have to be situated within a cross-cultural pattern of specialist stone working. Cf. ALEXANDER 1996 and REVEYRON 2003 for late medieval Europe.

¹⁷¹ PARIBENI 2004, 670; MARSILI 2019, 124.

¹⁷² Following Robert C. Allen, we assume that daily labourers worked 250 days per year, which is what was also assumed for early modern workers. This looks plausible in view of the large number of festivals in the late Roman empire (ALLEN 2009, 337).

¹⁷³ For Renaissance Florence, see GOLDTHWAITE 1980, 300-301.

¹⁷⁴ CROKE-CROW 1983, 148-151.

¹⁷⁵ ANON. *enarr. S. Sophiae* 1.9: «Μιλιαρίσια γὰρ ἀργυρᾶ καθ' ἐκάστην ἐκομίζοντο ἐκ τοῦ παλατίου καὶ ἐτίθοντο εἰς τὸ ὠρολογεῖον καὶ ὅσοι ἀνεβίβαζον λίθους, ἐλάμβανον καθ' ἐκάστην ἡμέραν ἀνὰ ἀργυροῦ ἑνός, διὰ τὸ μὴ ἀκηδιάσαι τινὰ ἐξ αὐτῶν ἢ βλασηγμήσαι». See also PATLAGEAN 1977, 172-173.

¹⁷⁶ MAGOULIAS 1976, 15.

¹⁷⁷ *Vita S. Symeoni Iunioris* 180: « Ἄνθρωπός τις τῶν ἐν ταῖς

οἰκοδομαῖς λιθοξοούντων τῆς πόλεως ἐσυλήθη τὸν αὐτοῦ κάματον χρυσίνους δώδεκα».

¹⁷⁸ MANGO 1976, 27.

¹⁷⁹ BERNARD 2017, 82-83.

¹⁸⁰ ZANINI 2007, 384.

¹⁸¹ Basically, in a labour market without tight regulations wages fall within a range determined by the relation between demand and supply, with slight variations occurring from job to job according to conditions of employment and the employer's disposition to spend. For Renaissance Florence, see GOLDTHWAITE 1980, 324.

¹⁸² Cf. GARNSEY 1998, 85-86 and DI BRANCO 2000, 193. The Harvard excavations at Sardis revealed intense building activity in the Western part of the city, which was completely renewed in Late Antiquity (FOSS 1979b, 39-66). The same conditions existed in early fourth-century Rome with the initiation of the massive Tetrarchic building program and the Maxentius' no less ambitious aspirations, in the context of which the inscription from Sant'Omobono should be placed (FABIANO 2019, 82-83).

The most useful discussion of prices and wages in the 5th and 6th centuries by Cécile Morrisson suggests, not by chance, that our stoneworkers could afford a decent standard of living¹⁸³. Data on wages, prices and the purchasing power of money are not easy to interpret, given the fluctuations in the exchange rate between the *solidus* and the subsidiary coinage¹⁸⁴. However, since we often have wheat prices, we can translate nominal wages into litres of wheat, which formed the basic element of the Roman and early Byzantine diet¹⁸⁵.

According to Robert C. Allen and Walter Scheidel, the ancient “respectability” consumption basket included an annual consumption of kilogram 172 of wheat (or kilogram 0.47 per day)¹⁸⁶. Diocletian’s Price Edict lists wheat at 100 *denarii* per *castrensis modius* (1 *c.m.* = ca. 13 litres of wheat), making the stonemason’s (λιθουργός τεχνίτης) maximum wage equivalent to 0.61 *c.m.* Including *pastus* or food allowance, the stonemason’s maximum daily wage in the Price Edict was litres 7.94 or ca. kilograms 6.1¹⁸⁷.

In the 5th and 6th centuries the average cost of one *modius* of wheat was between 1/36 or 1/42 *solidus*, indicating a certain stability in prices and the purchasing power of golden coinage¹⁸⁸. The above-mentioned quarryman Eulogios was therefore able to buy a *modius* of wheat with his daily wage of one *keration*. This conforms to the monthly pay scale of the stonecutters at the imperial granite quarries of *Mons Claudianus* in Egypt, where in the 2nd c. an average skilled worker earned 47 *drachmae* per month, more or less equivalent to the price of 5 *artabae* of wheat, a quantity sufficient to feed five people. Hence, this monthly pay easily met the cost of a “respectability” consumption basket¹⁸⁹.

Hence, skilled stoneworkers fell into the category of those self-employed artisans who – according to John Chrysostom – were better fed than wage labourers, because, he says, employers tended to cut a substantial part of the wages of the workers they employed¹⁹⁰. They were part of that class of “middling” persons who occupied the middle ground between the very rich and the very poor and included craftsmen, shopkeepers, low ranking state-employees, soldiers and non-commissioned officers, priests and clerics, as well as free peasants and tenants in the countryside¹⁹¹. Even though these middle-income persons lived under a constant threat of impoverishment, skilled craftsmen had better chances than unskilled labourers to put a comfortable distance between themselves and the poverty line.

«...ΤΗ ΙΔΙΑ ΔΙΑΛΕΚΤΩ»: THE IDENTITY OF STONEMASONS AND CARVERS

That stone-carvers were moderately prosperous individuals finds confirmation in the fact that some of them could afford a grave with an epitaph mentioning their trade and occupation. References to trades hold an important place in epitaphs from the 4th c. on, expressing the sense of belonging to a profession, which was an important part of an individual’s public persona and private identity alike¹⁹².

Late Antiquity also witnessed the strengthening of professional associations, membership to which is sometimes mentioned in funerary inscriptions¹⁹³. One of these associations is known from an inscription from the quarries of Proconnesos mentioning the imperial *ἐπίτροπος* Thalassos and the *ιερά τέχνη* (sacred guild) of the marble-workers¹⁹⁴. Another inscription found in a quarry between Corinth and Kenchreai expresses the gratitude of the stonecutters, sharpeners, and marble-workers towards a certain Theodosios, probably a local official, who renovated the city of Corinth, presumably because this had been very good for this people’s business (Fig. 8)¹⁹⁵.

¹⁸³ MORRISSON 1989.

¹⁸⁴ BANAJI 2015, 91-109.

¹⁸⁵ On the price of wheat in Late Antiquity, see DURLIAT 1990, 497-502.

¹⁸⁶ ALLEN 2009, 341, tab. 16.3; SCHEIDEL 2010, 434, tab. 2.

¹⁸⁷ BERNARD 2017, 81.

¹⁸⁸ Prices could rise two, three or six times in famine conditions (MORRISSON 1989, 257).

¹⁸⁹ CUVIGNY 1996, 140-141. See also BERNARD 2017, 80.

¹⁹⁰ IOA. CHRYS. *Hom. in Ep. I ad Cor.* 43.3: «Καθάπερ γὰρ ἐπὶ τῶν τεχνιτῶν οἱ μὲν ἑαυτοὺς τρέφοντες καὶ ἐργαζόμενοι, μείζονα τὸν μισθὸν λαμβάνουσιν, οἱ δὲ παρὰ τοῖς μισθωσαμένοις τρεφόμενοι, ὑποτέμνονται τοῦ μισθοῦ οὐ μικρὸν μέρος».

¹⁹¹ BROWN 2002, 48-50; SODINI 2003, 42-45.

¹⁹² MORRISSON-SODINI 2002, 201; SODINI 2003, 43-44.

¹⁹³ A funerary inscription from Korykos mentions the guild of the custom-house officials who deal with linen importers (*MAMA* III.771: + Τοῦ συσστήματος / τὸν εὐγενεστάτων / + τραπέζιτων +; see also TROMBLEY 1987, 18).

¹⁹⁴ «Ἀῖξει Προκόννησος τῷ αἰῶνι / Ἀῖξει ἱερά τέχνη τῷ αἰῶνι / Ἀῖξει Θεόδοσος ἐπίτροπος ὁ ἀναναιωτής» (ROBERT 1960, 26-27; ASGARI - DREW-BEAR 2002, 17-18).

¹⁹⁵ «Λιθ]οξά[ο]ι καὶ ἀκον[η]ταὶ / καὶ μαρ]μαράριοι εὐχαριστοῦντες / ἀνέθεντο] τὸ ἐγκώμιον /] αἶξει Θεοδόσ[ι]ε ἀνανεωντὰ πό[λι]ως / Κορίνθου μαλ[ί]ς καὶ κανπλικ[ς]» (MERITT 1931, 141, No. 245; ROBERT 1960, 21-24; ΛΑΜΠΡΟΠΟΥΛΟΥ 2018, 353-360; RIZOS 2021, 140-141).

Fig. 8. Quarry between Corinth and Kenchreai: inscription of acclamation of the local stonecutters, sharpeners, and marble workers celebrating “Theodosios, renewer of the city of Corinth” (after MERITT 1931; © The American School of Classical Studies at Athens).

This kind of professional associations defended corporate interests and sought to control the economy. Several imperial constitutions, paralleled in the Sardis inscription of AD 459, appear aimed at repressing the construction workers to create “cartels” with the intention of controlling the labour market and artificially determining price rises¹⁹⁶.

The development of associations reflects the professionalization of construction builders, which can be understood as the process by which producers of special services sought to constitute and control a market for their expertise¹⁹⁷. On the other hand, early Byzantine stone-carvers share some of the characteristics defining a proper “professional”: they are paid, full-time, involved prolonged training and a formal qualification or credentials; their practitioners are skilled, specialist, highly trained, of value to wider society, regulated, and share common ideals and identity¹⁹⁸.

In first place, stone-working required a long and highly multidisciplinary training and apprenticeship¹⁹⁹. None of the apprenticeship contracts surviving from the late antique world relate to stone-carving, but later Byzantine evidence place apprentices (*μαθητάδες*) under the supervision of master builders²⁰⁰.

Apprenticeship often took place within the apprentice’s own family group of origin. Funerary inscriptions from Korykos provide a sense of the familial and household strategies among early Byzantine artisans. Mobility between different craft trades appear to have been limited by family ties. Epitaphs often

¹⁹⁶ GARNSEY 1998, 84-85; DI BRANCO 2000, 191-194.

¹⁹⁷ According to the definition of the sociologist Magali Sarfatti Larson quoted by RUSSELL 2020, 246-247.

¹⁹⁸ *Ibid.*, 246.

¹⁹⁹ Apprentices usually served for approximately five to ten years learning the trade, and in return received a board, lodging and often clothing. In some cases, they also earned a small salary as their skills developed, even if these wages were well below the market rate (FREU 2011; HAWKINS 2016, 176-177, 199-202; RUSSELL 2020, 251-252).

On the formation of building workers in the pre-modern world, cf. PRAK 2011, 398-403.

²⁰⁰ In the *Hypomnemata* of Hosios Loukas, each master had his own apprentice. The fact that boys acting as helpers were a regular part of a construction workshop in Byzantine finds confirmation in several tenth-to-fifteenth-century decrees from Mount Athos. When *oikodomoí* were summoned to work at the monasteries, boys and “beardless youths” were not allowed to join – apparently to safeguard the morals of the monks (OUSTERHOUT 1999, 52-53).

mention individuals who were relatives and workmates at the same time: fathers and sons practiced the same trade in most cases attested²⁰¹. In the case of stone-carving, this practice is already attested to in ancient Greece, and in the Roman period we know several examples of families of stone-carvers stretching over multiple generations²⁰².

Carving workshops were essentially small, family enterprises with a handful of workers and apprentices coordinated and supervised by a master²⁰³. Within these workshops, there was a certain degree of labour division and specialisation, and each stage in the production could have been split between different carvers²⁰⁴. Apprentices and junior carvers might have undertaken the initial stages of roughing out, while the master carver and his assistants were responsible for the bulk of carving out right up the final stages²⁰⁵.

This kind of organisation contributed to strengthening the sense of identity of the members of single workshops, no less important than their broader collective professional identity. Masons' marks were a mode for expressing identity: workshops could stick to certain basic shapes and adapt them for their successive members²⁰⁶.

The bonds of corporate solidarity were also expressed through invocations on building materials pleading for protection and prosperity for the members of workshops and professional associations²⁰⁷, perhaps like that incised by one of the teams which worked for the construction of the Hagia Sophia, on a column base of the southern colonnade of Great Church in Constantinople: «Κύριε βοήθει τῷ ἐργαστηρίῳ» («Lord, help the workshop») (Fig. 9)²⁰⁸. A similar example is offered by a sixth/seventh-century text inscribed on a window-mullion from Vaphes Apokoronou near Chania (Crete) asking God to remember the saints Cosmas and Damianos, the future visitors of their shrine and the artisans who built the shrine itself²⁰⁹.

The hagiographies of certain saints suggest, moreover, that their cults were associated with specific professional groups²¹⁰. In the case of stoneworkers, the saints Florus and Laurus are described as λιθόξοοι in their martyrdom account composed in the 6th/7th c.²¹¹. The twin brothers came from Byzantium to *Ulpiana* in *Dardania*, where they worked in the local quarries before being summoned for the building of a temple. Once the work was completed, Florus and Laurus entered the temple at night and consecrated the temple as a church, destroying all the idols. This triggered pagan reaction, and the two brothers were then thrown into a well and buried alive²¹². Later their relics were taken from *Ulpiana* to Constantinople, where their heads were kept at the monastery of Pantokrator²¹³.

It is likely that Florus and Laurus were venerated as the patrons of stonemasons and builders, much like their Roman equivalent, the Four Crowned Martyrs²¹⁴. Devotion to specific saints helped to maintain the bonds of collective identity, which may be characterized as a multilayered and multifaceted construct

²⁰¹ PATLAGEAN 1977, 168. However, pursuing the same trade as one's father is not the same as joining the family business but, at least in these cases, we can see how training was pursued down through generations (HAWKINS 2016, 203-227).

²⁰² RUSSELL 2020, 253.

²⁰³ The finds from the so-called Sculptor's Workshop at Aphrodisias, probably running as early as the mid-2nd c. up until the end of the 4th c., comprise several roughly carved feet and a few hands, which appear to be training pieces used by apprentices (*Id.* 2013, 347; VAN VOORHIS 2018).

²⁰⁴ On labour division in carving workshops, see RUSSELL 2013, 250-254 and MARANO 2015, 999-1001 (for sarcophagi production). That the finishing of details required a high degree of specialisation is illustrated by a passage of the *Life of Symeon the Younger*, in which a certain John, who had no previous experience of stone carving, was divinely inspired, like another Bezaleel, to do the complicated carving on the capitals of the main church of the monastery on the Wondrous Mountain (*Vita S. Symeonis Iunioris* 108: «Ἀδελφῶ τινι τῶν μαθητῶν τοῦ μακαρίου Συμεῶν, Ἰωάννη τοῦνομα, ἐδόθη διὰ τῆς εὐχῆς τοῦ ἁγίου πνεύματος σοφίας ὡς τῷ Βεσελεὴλ ἐπὶ τῷ γλύφει ποικίλως τὰς κεφαλίδας τῶν κίωνων τῆς ἐκκλησίας τῆς παρὰ τοῦ ἁγίου οικοδομηθείσης καὶ ἐπικληθείσης ἐπὶ τῷ ὀνόματι τῆς ἁγίας καὶ ζωοποιῆς τριάδος»).

²⁰⁵ However, on a large and complex project like Hagia Sophia, there are signs on the most elaborate pieces (as, for example, the capitals of the colonnades and exedras of the ground-floor and the galleries) suggesting that multiple carvers could have worked on them simultaneously. This is also confirmed by the presence of more than one masons' marks on the same element (MARSILI 2019, 122).

²⁰⁶ PARIBENI 2004, 666-667. J.-P. Sodini has observed that masons' marks remained in use within the context of a generation, and when it is possible to follow the use of specific marks for more than a generation, they should be referred to the successors or apprentices of a master (SODINI 1989, 168).

²⁰⁷ RIZOS 2021, 145.

²⁰⁸ ANTONΙΑΔΟΥ 1907, 209.

²⁰⁹ «Μνίστι(τι) Κ(ύρι)ε τῶν Ἁγίων Ἐν/αργύρο Κοσμᾶ καὶ Δαμι/ανοῦ καὶ τὸ συνδραμό / το εἰς τιν κτίσιν αὐτῶν. / ἐντεκτιῶ(νος) α', ἐπὲ τοῦ / ἰγρωτάτου ἐπισκόπου Ἐπιφανίου(ν). / vacat / μνίστι(τι) Κ(ύρι)ε / καὶ τὸν τεχρίτων / +» (SEG 59.1058 = ΜΥΛΟΠΟΤΑΜΙΤΑΚΙ 2000 = P. Nowakowski, *Cult of Saints*, E04545 - <http://csla.history.ox.ac.uk/record.php?recid=E04545>).

²¹⁰ RIZOS 2016.

²¹¹ On the hagiographic dossier of the saints Florus and Laurus, which comprise five recensions of a *passio* (BHG 660-664), see RIZOS 2016, 207-212. Italian translations of the main recensions, without the Greek text, can be found in BRESSI-VOTTO 1998.

²¹² RIZOS 2016, 207-208.

²¹³ The monastery's fifth feast day, August 18, was dedicated to Florus and Laurus, as we know from the *Synaxarium Ecclesiae Constantinopolitanae* and the account of a number of Russian travellers (KOTZABASSI 2013, 160).

²¹⁴ The two hagiographies recount essentially the same story and can be regarded as derivation of a common legendary source reflecting the cultural background of the Middle Danube and its hinterland in Late Antiquity (RIZOS 2016, 208). On the Four Crowned Martyrs, cf. GUYON 1975 and LAPIDGE 2018, 448-667.

Fig. 9. Istanbul, Hagia Sophia, southern colonnade: graffito with an invocation on behalf of workshop (after ANTONIAΔΟΥ 1907).

that included professional, religious, regional/ethnic, familiar, and personal identities. This is particularly apparent in the case of Isaurian stoneworkers.

The term “Isaurian” was a sort of umbrella-like label, describing the broad range of ethnic identities that existed in the mountain region north of the Cilician coast²¹⁵. Moreover, literary sources show how Isaurian were perceived by external observers and say little of what being Isaurian meant for the Isaurians themselves. If being an Isaurian was a matter of descent and geography, both vague criteria, amenable to invention and denial as individuals felt necessary, this does not mean that the Isaurians did not share some common and peculiar traits. However, military prowess and banditry, two of the things the Isaurians were famous for, were not obviously determined by ethnicity, but by the socioeconomic conditions of their region of origin, and the same applies to stoneworkers²¹⁶.

As seen, Isauria was rich in limestone and witnessed intense building activity during Late Antiquity. Isaurian soldiers, bandits and stoneworkers must have acted as solidarity-groups, not because of their provenance, but because of their professional activity. This solidarity is, for example, manifest in the episode recounted in the *Life of Symeon the Younger* about the member of the Isaurian stonemasons working in Antioch, who was taken by his companion before the saint for being hailed²¹⁷. Indeed, one has the impression of a small, itinerant group in which everyone took care of each other. Hence, the social networks of the workshop provided a setting for life at destination, a basis for solidarity and mutual aid²¹⁸.

Language was another central factor for the persistence and self-representation of Isaurian identity. There are no inscriptions preserved in any Isaurian language, a branch of Hittite now called Luwian²¹⁹. The only piece of evidence for this language being spoken is offered by a passage in the *Life of Symeon the Younger* of Isaurians using their own dialect («τῆ ἰδίᾳ διαλέκτῳ») when describing a miracle²²⁰. The very lack of evidence for it suggest Isaurian language had no value except for communication within Isaurian groups, i.e. it only helped determine group membership, and constituted an aspect of Isaurian identity²²¹. It is also worth noting that the *Life of Symeon the Younger* refer to Isaurian stoneworkers from the village of Kouvramon hinting to the existence of settlements which specialised in single crafts²²². This adds a further element to the identity of stonemasons and carvers from Isauria.

Finally, skill was an important concept for craftsmen themselves since it served as a key element in self-identity. They designated themselves by occupational labels (λιθοζόος, μαρμαράριος, οικοδόμος τεχνίτης, etc.)²²³, which occurs in “signatures” or, more accurately, “makers’ marks”, was not simply aimed at describing what they did, because these labels also signalled their status, since labour was a sign of social place as well as to survival and material accumulation²²⁴.

²¹⁵ SHAW 1990, 200-203.

²¹⁶ ELTON 2000, 300-301.

²¹⁷ OUSTERHOUT 1999, 51.

²¹⁸ This solidarity was probably strengthened by the fact that when construction works did not progress according to the expectations of the local communities, itinerant craftsmen – who came from the outside – were often blamed for the problems. For a later comparison from modern Finland, see VIIHANIEMI 2018, 151.

²¹⁹ BURGESS 1990, 113-115.

²²⁰ Vita S. Symeoni Iunioris 189: «Ὁ δὲ παραχρήμα γέγονεν ὑγιῆς βλω τῷ σώματι καὶ ἐκτείνας τὰς χεῖρας ἐδέξατο τὰ παρ’ αὐτοῦ ἐπιδοθέντα. Θεασάμενοι δὲ οἱ ἄλλοι τὸ γενόμενον παράδοξον σημεῖον ἤραν ὁμοθυμαδὸν τὴν φωνὴν αὐτῶν τῆ ἰδίᾳ διαλέκτῳ, εἰς οὐρανοῦς ἀναβλέποντες καὶ τὰς χεῖρας ἐκτείνοντες καὶ κράζοντες».

²²¹ Further evidence for shared tradition and values is offered by the use of peculiar personal names. The names attested in Isauria can be

divided into non-Greek, often theophoric names derived from Luwian gods, and Greek and Latin forms occurring frequently in the region, such as Zeno and Conon (BURGESS 1990, 114-121; ELTON 2000, 294).

²²² The development of similar settlements confirms the economic complexity of Isauria, where these villages, specialized in the production of particular categories of artefacts and in one trade, formed interdependent part of a regional economic unit through exchange (ROWLANDS 1971, 219).

²²³ Several of these “signatures” are known from the area of Laodicea and Apamea in Syria (JALABERT-MOUTERDE 1955, 208, No. 1619; 284-285, No. 1811; 318-319, No. 1900; 319, No. 1902; 340, No. 1957).

²²⁴ For the importance of skill to the identities of ancient artisans and craftsmen, see TRAN 2011, 121-128; for late Medieval and early Modern Europe, FARR 2000, 3-5.

FINAL REMARKS

Groups of itinerant stonemasons and carvers are known from several geographical areas and different historical periods. But, as said, we should not assume the existence of an all-embracing model for the organisation of a craft, as local and regional variations in phenomena such as politics, economic structure, settlement patterns and population may all impact on the manners in which a craft is organised, not to mention the impact of competition, market forces, topography, and access to raw materials. The differentiation between the various single groups of craftsmen can be assigned to the nature of, and the demand for, their products, as well as to the nature of production, and the natural differences between producers.

Notwithstanding this diversity, it is possible to highlight several specific points characterising the activity of stonemasons and carvers in the early Byzantine empire. These craftsmen operated in very different contexts (as obvious, the erection of Hagia Sophia at Constantinople cannot be equated to that of a church in one of the villages of the Limestone Massif of northeast Syria). However, the social, economic, and technical complexity of the building industry can hardly be underestimated at all levels. It represented the largest sector in the ancient economy, apart from the production and distribution of food²²⁵. According to an estimate by Janet DeLaine, 4 to 6 percent of the total population of Severan Rome worked in the building industry²²⁶. It is very likely that this estimate can be also applied to Constantinople, where building activity reached its climax between the 4th and 6th c.²²⁷. Moreover, much of the building materials (bricks, mortar, marble and stone, timber, fuel, etc.) were produced in the countryside and transported to urban centres using animal and human labour offered by rural households²²⁸. At the same time, individual members of smallholding families could find temporary employment as unskilled workforce in urban construction, before returning to the countryside once the works were completed²²⁹. In the building trade, “urban” and “rural” cannot therefore be neatly differentiated.

Similarly, the construction and maintenance of secular and, above all, religious buildings required significant investment, in cities as in the countryside²³⁰. As part of a broad imperial euergetic programme, particularly in the 6th c., fortifications, church buildings, waterworks and other urban projects feature prominently in the East. Provincial capitals and other centres of political, strategic, and religious relevance benefitted materially and financially from their position within the empire²³¹. Even in rural context, building activity contributed to the mobilisation of financial resources, though on a smaller scale²³². The economic multiplier of large expenditure on buildings and infrastructure would most readily be seen in the in the levels of employment in the construction industry.

Resources were indeed invested first and foremost in the payment of labour²³³. Construction itself required numerous unskilled workers²³⁴, but – given its temporary and seasonal nature – they would not have been able to sustain themselves during the slack period of the year. However, if seasonal rhythms were largely predictable, building activity, especially with regard to major projects, had an episodic character, and labourers were largely dependent upon the occasional calls of their patrons.

These two factors also influenced the decisions and livelihood of specialised and skilled craftsmen like our stonemasons and carvers. However, as seen, they could win high wages through their corporate strength, which was also rooted in the instability of their employment. Moreover, compared to unskilled workers, they were often paid a piece rate rather than a daily wage, and this allowed them to live above a subsistence standard.

Skilled stonemasons and carvers certainly benefitted from the stimulating effect that secular and ecclesiastic euergetism had on the economy as a whole²³⁵. In this respect, itinerancy was an important contributing element of their trade and one of the strategies adopted by them to navigate the economic environment

²²⁵ Obviously, also textile production was a key part of all ancient societies, but its archaeological traces are comparatively scanty (ERDKAMP 2012, 248-253).

²²⁶ The same Author calculates that in and around Rome at least between 25.000 to 30.000 workers were involved directly in the building trade and the supply of materials (DELAINE 1997, 197-201).

²²⁷ STRIKER *et alii* 2008.

²²⁸ ERDKAMP 2012, 252.

²²⁹ *Id.* 2016, 40.

²³⁰ For an appreciation of the importance of building activity in the economy of a late antique capital, see COSENTINO 2020 on Ravenna.

²³¹ MUNDELL MANGO 2003, 120. See also ZANINI 2021, 141-154.

²³² On the East, see JACOBS 2020a, 14; on Africa, DOSSEY 2010, 77-93.

²³³ ZANINI 2021, 143-144.

²³⁴ P.A. Brunt was the first to suggest that Rome's building sector used causal wage labour to meet the uneven but sometimes high demand for unskilled workers (BRUNT 1980, 92-94). In this regard, it is worth citing Justinian's *Novella* 80 of AD 535, according to which able-bodied men who came to Constantinople in search of a better livelihood were to be put to work in public works, in the state bakeries, market gardeners, and in other public services – «*et operum publicorum artibus ad ministerium et praepositis panificantium stationum et hortos operantibus aliisque diversis artibus aut operibus*» (PATLAGEAN 1977, 181).

²³⁵ *Ibid.*, 196-203.

in which they operated. Broadly speaking, itinerancy functioned well in response to idiosyncratic fluctuations in demand. Stonemasons and carvers were ready to move whenever an employment opportunity presented to them. They were fundamentally mobile though anchored to one place rather than peripatetic.

Skilled workers relied on communication networks capable of circulating information on labour market conditions over wide geographical areas²³⁶. In the case of Constantinopolitan carvers, the State played a central role in organising their employment and long-distance movements, while Isaurian stoneworkers commonly drew on a well-established circuit in which migrant workers retained their contacts with the home-base and provided valuable information facilitating movements on interregional scale. Information exchange was equally important in the much more restricted area of the Limestone Massif of northeast Syria, where socioeconomic structures preclude facile separation between skilled and unskilled workers. The village – inhabited by a stratum of peasants, who were prosperous enough to participate directly in commercial exchange – was the local unit of social organisation and inscriptions record the completion of many buildings in them, often undertaken by village organisation itself. Communal building projects, churches in first place, functioned simultaneously as expressions of group solidarity and commemorations of the differential contributions of the various members of the community. Buildings were not only a means to advertise one's wealth and social position through gifts and dedicatory inscriptions, but also a way to assert one's professional skills, as the makers' marks of stonemasons and carvers demonstrate. Demand for skilled building workers created, therefore, the conditions for their professional and social affirmation and contributed to strengthening their identity. This can be understood as a reflection of the homogeneity of early Byzantine architecture that, notwithstanding the multivocality so apparent in the artistic production of the 5th to 7th centuries, depended on a relatively homogeneous economic environment and on similar forms of labour.

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